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The Akkadian Vocabulary of Noah's Ark and its Allegorical and Ritual Significance

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Abstract

The Genesis account of Noah's Ark has long engendered a debate over the relationship between the Hebrew story and the older cuneiform flood myths. In English, this famed craft is called "*the ark*". However, the phrase used in the Hebrew text is "התבה" (*htbh*, Masoretic *hatebah*), for which no Hebrew etymology exists. Here I present evidence that "תבה" transcribes Akkadian "*Tabû*", represented by the logograms "*ZI*" and "*I.ZI.A*"—which have the constituent Sumerian meanings of "*Life*", "*To Lead out Life (from) Water*" and "*To Overcome Annihilation*".^{1,2,3} It is part of a cuneiform semantic field that identifies the Great Flood as a repurposed metaphor for the destruction of Israel. The language details signal that the Hebraic version was originally conceptualized in cuneiform during the 6th century BC as part of a ritual invoking the rescue of the nation from exile in Babylon.

Keywords: Genesis, the Great Flood, Noah's Ark, Mesopotamia, Mythology, Allegory, Akkadian, Sumerian, Ancient Hebrew, Cuneiform wordplay, Biblical magic, Barû ritual, Judean Akîtu festival, Babylonian exile, Semiotics

1. Introduction

In the 1870s, English scholar George Smith published translations of a set of cuneiform tablets that included a Mesopotamian version of the flood story (Smith, 1876). Many of the

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¹ Tabû can also be expressed logographically as "*ZI.GA*", which sounds like "*House of Life*" in Sumerian (*zi.ga₂*). "*ZI*" signifies "*breath of life*"; "*zi-i*" (with the final consonant dropped) means "*to annihilate*"; "*i*" means "*cry of pain, capture, defeat, to overcome, to bring out*", "*a*" is "*water*" (CAD, SL).

² Chicago Assyrian Dictionary (CAD)—Roth MT (2010).

³ Sumerian Lexicon (SL)—Halloran (1999).

details were similar or identical to the Genesis account. This sparked speculation over which came first, or whether both descended from a common oral or written tradition. In the 150 years that have elapsed since then, many cuneiform versions of the story have been discovered, dating back to circa 2300 BC. These include accounts in Sumerian, which predates Akkadian (although the languages overlapped in time). The age and historical continuity of these tablets establish their precedence (Finkel, 2014). Nevertheless, the relationship between the Genesis account and the older cuneiform versions remains enigmatic.

Before the discovery of these tablets, the nomenclatural origin of the watercraft was sought in Aramaic or Egyptian. Although Hebrew “תבה” (*tebah*) has an etymological link to Aramaic “תיבותא” (*tibuta*), Targum Onkelos (an early Aramaic translation) uses the Hebrew word in the Genesis text while the Aramaic variant is written in the gloss (OR 2363). This indicates that the latter is simply an Aramaized form of the Hebrew. The possibility of an Egyptian origin is suggested by the reappearance the “תבה” as a “*basket made of bulrushes*” in the story of the infant Moses (Exod. 2:3, RSV). Nevertheless, no credible Egyptian linguistic source has been found.^{4,5}

Logically, the origin of the ark name is connected to the source of the story. If “*tebah*” is not a native Hebrew word, the obvious place to search is the older Mesopotamian accounts. However, none of these use the word “*tebah*”—or anything similar. The vessel is usually called “*boat*”—which is “*ma*” (^{giš}*ma*₂) in Sumerian and “*eleppu*” in Akkadian. This leaves us without a cognate of “*tebah*” in the oldest versions of the story.

Irving Finkel (2014) proposed Akkadian “*ṭubbû*”, a kind of river boat, interpreting the substitution of “ת” (*t*) for “ט” (*ṭ*) in “תבה” (*tb* instead of *ṭb*) as a sound shift arising from the Hebraization of the loanword (pp. 197-201). Although “*ṭubbû*” is a good match, it does not appear in any of the Mesopotamian flood narratives. Finkel posits the existence of a lost source of the Ark story that employed this term. If this word did in fact occur in a late version, it would mean that it was selected for use in the Hebraic version in preference to the classical terms. While this is possible, the fact that we don't have this hypothetical version suggests instead an innovation on the part of the Genesis author(s).

⁴ The Brown-Driver-Briggs Lexicon (citing Erman Brugsch, 1892) lists “*tb̄t*” as a possible Egyptian source of the Hebrew word (Driver et al, 2006). The Dictionary of Late Egyptian (Lesco, 2002) defines “*tb*” as “*box*” or “*cage*”, while “*tḥbst*” means “*basket*”. The Gesenius “תבה” (1857) entry concludes with the statement, “*The etymology is unknown*”. No viable Egyptian roots have emerged since then.

⁵ The English word “*ark*” comes from Latin “*arca*” (a wooden box), which was mistakenly used in the Vulgate (Vulgata Clementina) for both Noah's ark (תבה—*tebah*) and the ark (ארון—*aron*) of the covenant (Bellarmino, 1592). A different word (*fiscella*) is employed for Moses' ark (תבה). English translations commonly follow suit by merging the two unrelated words while separating the vocabulary of the two stories that use the same term.

The Genesis retelling of this Mesopotamian myth implies a purpose behind the peculiar word choices that diverge from the cuneiform templates. In this case, the author would necessarily have been an accomplished scribe (and likely a member of a group of kindred scribes) who knew the cuneiform stories but chose a different Akkadian word for the Hebraic version.

Most modern scholars take the view that all the stories of Genesis descend from an ancient Hebrew oral tradition (Beck et al. 1995). With regard to the Ark account, Finkel's work challenges this longstanding assumption by demonstrating the incorporation of terminology from Mesopotamian predecessors. The borrowed Mesopotamian boat-building vocabulary (such as *kupru*—the “כפר” waterproofing of the ark) is very specific and is only used in this particular story of the Hebrew Bible. It is extremely unlikely that terminology that is culturally and ecologically tied to Mesopotamia would have survived centuries of oral transmission in a foreign land before being recorded in writing.

The presence of nautical words without referent in the Hebrew lexicon points to a written adaptation of the Mesopotamian accounts. The constellation of circumstances necessary for such an endeavor further suggests written composition during the Judean exile in Babylon (Finkel, 2014)—which is much later in the historical timeline than is commonly thought. This challenges the long-held views of scholars (who see distinctive traces of pre-exilic Israelite religious beliefs in the story) and traditionalists (who are deeply invested in Mosaic authorship). The fact that Moses himself is a child of the “Ark” suggests that both of these views need to be reexamined.

Among people of Abrahamic faith (Orthodox Jews, Christians, Muslims) the Genesis flood story and its details are taken as part and parcel of a historical event. An assortment of archaeological expeditions to Mt. Ararat (the final resting place of Noah's Ark) and the development of an Ark tourism niche in modern Turkey reflect this assumption of historicity. The internal logic of this perspective requires a correspondence between the material details (read literally) and an actual historical watercraft. Curiously, neither the classic Mesopotamian ark designations (*ma*, *eleppu*) nor any of the usual Hebrew words for boat appear in the Genesis flood account.

In this sense, the unexplained word translated as “ark” offers the key to the story. The vocabulary of the Hebraic Ark suggests that it belongs neither to history (because of the story's intrinsic symbolism) nor to oral folklore (because the foreign loanwords are directly linked to older written accounts). The alternative is that the Ark (inclusive of its material and narrative details) was meant figuratively. Indeed, its iconic nature is immediately grasped by most readers (including children)—making Noah's Ark the subject of countless classroom drawings and museum art works.

The account is widely interpreted today as a metaphor of impending doom—with the fate of the planet hanging in the balance. The modern environmental movement (and Hollywood)

perceives the Great Flood as an ancient warning against a cataclysm provoked by man's misbehavior. Hence, the Ark is understood as a model for the preservation of species (Harper, 2021). Although symbolic quality of the myth is unmistakable, the ancient audience (or public performers) of the story had their own concerns. As we shall see, the Deluge narrative addresses these.

The fact that this iconic account was written in the first place requires a set of motivating circumstances that is intrinsically connected to the time-setting of authorship. Given that the Mesopotamian story was rewritten multiple times by different ethnic groups in different languages, we can infer that each distinct rendition expresses nuances typifying the eras of authorship. This observation is a statement of the obvious. The modern environmental interpretation of this myth is a case in point. If we peel back the layers, we may be able to identify the purpose of the oldest known written version—which then served as a model that was either followed or selectively changed in later versions. The Hebraic account fits somewhere in this pattern.

Connecting the pieces of ancient puzzles is challenging. Modern archaeology is criticized for relying upon artifacts (such as pottery) to date strata that are then used to date the artifacts (Di Angelo et al. 2022). With regard to understanding the cultural context of the Hebrew Bible, archaeological finds have often been fitted to the narrative timeline (Finkelstein, 2002 and Dever, 2005 vs. Mazar, 2018). Although the Bible contains a trove of historical information, its structured arrangement is literary. Hence, the timeline does not necessarily proceed in historical order. The arrangement was always more mutable than most readers (and many scholars) realize.

Scholarship dedicated to tracing the development of the Hebrew text of Genesis runs up against an apparent archaeological boundary. No biblical manuscripts pre-dating the exile of Judah in Babylon (c. 586 BC) have been found, although the priestly benediction (Num. 6:22-26) is discernible in the alternative context of protective amulets (Barkay et al. 2004; cf. Ps. 67:1). Radio carbon dating of the Dead Sea scrolls indicates that none were written before 350 BC, with 250 BC being the more probable upper limit (Langlois, 2019). Epigraphic analysis of fragments written in the Old Hebrew script gives an upper limit of the 5th or 4th centuries BC (ibid, pp. 276-277). Thus, textual analysis of the presumed ancient Hebrew of Genesis is limited by the absence of ancient material for comparison.

In contrast, the continuous record of cuneiform writing across several millennia offers an unparalleled source of hard information. The discovery of tens of thousands of cuneiform tablets in the ruins of various eras gives us a vast number of data points with which to work. Cuneiform signs and syllabic word forms changed incrementally during 3,000 years of use. If Genesis indeed belongs to the cuneiform tradition, it should be quite possible to date the

composition. The details of the vocabulary, the associated signs and the plot itself potentially provide an interrelated time stamp.

Cuneiform inscriptions found outside an archaeological context can often be dated with relative confidence. We can be sure that earlier scribes had no knowledge of later sign forms. On the other hand, the existence of archives in temples and royal palaces gave later scribes the ability to access older cuneiform records. In other words, the existence of a clay tablet written in an older form does not necessarily prove an older date of composition—or the recopying an older work. If such a tablet is found in a stratum of a particular time period, we know that it is at least as old as the ruins. However, it may be no older than that. Akkadian scribes were quite capable of composing new *ouvrés* in Sumerian. In contrast, the use of newer sign shapes and syllabic vocalizations is diagnostic of more recent work.

Given the Mesopotamian origin of the Deluge account recorded in Genesis, there is a compelling logic for searching these sources for the vocabulary of Noah's Ark. As in archaeological reconstructions, however, the etymological reconstruction of language risks conforming to an expected outcome. That being said, the discovery of an underlying cuneiform stratum of the Hebraic account of Noah's Ark constitutes an unexpected outcome in relation to conventional scholarship—although it ought not to be so. The details of the cuneiform vocabulary (Akkadian, Sumerian and symbolic) fit a specific cultural context and political era that illuminates the story and provides a reason for why it was written.

The earliest cuneiform versions describe conflicts between the gods and the subsequent creation of mankind, which then leads to the Deluge. This backstory explains why the flood occurred. The Hebraic Ark and Flood account is likewise a distinct story that is also part of a broader narrative sequence. In Genesis, Noah's Ark follows after the account of the Garden of Eden, but precedes the Tower of Babel and the patriarchal cycle. Each episode in this series shares the themes of sin, punishment and exile (Hendel, 1987)—with the survival of a righteous remnant. Given the narrative position of the Ark story in this sequence, we should not be surprised to find that Hebrew phrase “התבה” (*htbh*) is connected to these themes.

2. Language Background

The Hebrew language has many Akkadian loanwords, most of which were acquired during the 6th century BC exile of Judah in Babylon. Both are Semitic languages: Hebrew is classified as West Semitic, while Akkadian is East Semitic. The phonetic and grammatical shifts between cognate words in these two branches have been worked out in great detail (Hasselbach-Andee and Pat-El, 2021). For the purposes of our reconstruction, the most important shift occurs at the end of words.

Akkadian words typically have a terminal “u” that is dropped in Hebrew cognates.⁶ We see this in the Akkadian month names Abu, Nisānu and Ṭebētu, which became Ab, Nisan and Ṭebet in Hebrew. The exchange is reversed in West Semitic words that entered Akkadian following the Amorite conquests of the 3rd and 2nd millennia BC (Gelb, 1961). Examples include “*ammu*” (people), “*azāru*” (help) and “*nadāru*” (vow), which correspond to West Semitic “*am*”, “*ezer*” and “*neder*”.⁷

Borrowed foreign terms that were understood as feminine in Hebrew were transcribed with the suffix “ה” (*h*) or plural “ות” (*ot*). This transposition also appears in cases where there is an equivalent Hebrew word that is not feminine but yet possesses a terminal “ה”. For example, the Assyrian king sent an official called “רב־שקה” (*Rb-šqh*) to Jerusalem during the reign of Hezekiah (2 Kgs. 18:17). The Hebrew form translates the Akkadian title “*Rab Šāqū*”—“*Chief Libationer*” (aka *Cup Bearer*) while showing the influence of the corresponding indigenous term, “משקה” (*mašqeh*).^{2,8}

If we reconstruct the Hebrew ark (תבה—*tebah*) on the basis of this borrowing pattern, the terminal “h” is restored to “u”, giving us “*tebu*”. In this case, the suffix “ה” would have been substituted during transcription from Akkadian to Hebrew based on the object’s identification as a “*ship*”—Hebrew “אנייה” (*aniyah*), which is conceptually feminine. “*Tebû*” means “*To set out, depart, leave, to rise up in revolt, to rebel*”.² It is written syllabically as “*te-bu-ú*” but can also be expressed with the logogram “*ZI*”—representing “*Life*”. The longer form is “*I.ZI.A*”, signifying “*To bring out the Life*” and “*To lead out Life (from) Water*” in Sumerian.^{2,9}

The missing meaning of “*boat*” is supplied via a wordplay on “*ṭēbû*”—an alternate form of Irving Finkel’s “*ṭubbû*”.⁷ Since the Akkadian “*t*” (ת) is retained in Hebrew “*tebah*” (תבה), the word “*tebû*” can be taken as the primary form—making it a pun on the “*ṭēbû*” boat. This shifts the emphasis from the type of watercraft to its metaphorical meaning. The Neo-Babylonian (NB) form of the word is “*tabû*”.⁷ This evokes “*TAB.U*” as a combined syllabogram/logogram representing the watercraft. “*TAB*” (𐎶) is the number “*two*”, while “*U*” (𐎵) represents “*ten*”. Thus, the Hebraic Ark embodies the number “*twelve*” (שתיים עשרה—*two-ten*), corresponding to the tribes of Israel. These meanings signal that the Ark is an allegorical vehicle—an instrument of rescue from a Great Flood of a different order.¹⁰

⁶ The discussion here regards nouns. For the *-u* suffix in verbs, see Bjøru and Pat-El (2021).

⁷ Concise Dictionary of Akkadian (CDA)—Black J, George A and Postgate N (2000).

⁸ The formal Hebrew title is “שר המשקים” (*šar Mašqim*, cf. Gen. 41:9). The more common term “משקה” is used by Nehemiah, the cup-bearer of Ahasuerus (Neh. 1:11, cf. Gen. 40:1).

⁹ “*A*” (𐎶) means water, but also functions as a definite article/nominalizing suffix (Sumerian Lexicon).

¹⁰ The literary use of the cataclysmic flood as a metaphor for the conquest and the destruction of the beloved homeland is a prominent theme in Sumerian literature (cf. the Lament for Urim, Lament for Sumer and Urim, Lament for Unug).

The cuneiform semantic field associated with the restoration of “*tabû*” as the Hebraic “*ark*” opens a veritable Pandora’s Box. The nature of the text, the timeline of writing and the theological framework of Genesis are each profoundly reshaped by this field. The sense of uprising and escape lies at the heart of the only other occurrence of the word in the Hebrew Bible. Like Noah, Moses’ mother built a boat called *tabû* (*ZI = life*). She placed her infant son in it to save him from death (Exod. 2:1-3). Although the materials of the Ark of Moses appear different, they belong to the same cuneiform semantic field as Noah’ Ark.^{3,11,12,13,14} Moses went on to instigate a slave revolt and lead his people out (*tabû*) of “Egypt”.¹⁵

In both cases (Moses and Noah), the nation had to first pass through water in order to obtain life. This commonality establishes the symbolic nature of the accounts—which can then be understood as carefully crafted variations of the same invocational allegory. Israel survived while Pharaoh and the Egyptian army drowned in the inundating sea, mirroring the fate of the wicked during the Great Flood—in contradistinction to the fate of the righteous family (Gen. 6:5-8, Exod. 15:9). The recurrence of the same story set in different eras shifts the date of composition much farther down the timeline. It also signals that the geographic place-setting of Egypt mirrors the Mesopotamian setting of the first of the paired narratives.

3. Why has the Possibility of an Underlying Cuneiform Text been Disregarded?

The idea of cuneiform origins for parts of the Bible is not new. Arthur Crowley (1923) proposed that pre-exilic biblical texts were kept on clay tablets (xxvii, xxvi-footnote 1). P.J. Wiseman (1936) explored the hypothesis that the Book of Genesis originated as a collation of a series of cuneiform tablets—as suggested by its episodic nature. However, neither writer provided supporting language analyses. W.F. Albright (1918) dismissed earlier “*theories*”

¹¹ These materials include “זפת” (*zpt*) ← Akk. “*zapītu*” (a kind of *rush*, also *watch-tower*), invoking the favor of the divine judge Šamaš (*šapītu*), and “חמר” (*hmr*) waterproofing ← Akk. “*hamāru*” (to *dry out*) with “*hummuru*” (*KUD.SIL.DU*)—“to *decide*, to *separate*” + “to *praise* (= *Judah*)” + “to *go*”. Note that “*KUD.SIL*” is an alternate reading of “*KUD.KUD*” (CAD, CDA, CSL, SL, ePSD).

¹² Cuneiform Sign List (CSL)—Šašková, K. 2015.

¹³ Sum. “*kud*” also signifies “to *curse*” (SL). “*KUD.SIL.DU*” (*hmr*) signals Judah’s escape from the curse.

¹⁴ Pennsylvania Sumerian Dictionary, electronic version (ePSD)—Tinney S (2006).

¹⁵ The Akkadian language and narrative link between Genesis and Exodus suggest that “*Egypt*” is an allegorical substitute for Babylon. Out of 586 occurrences of “מצרים” (*Mšrym*) in the Hebrew scriptures, 227 appear in the phrase “ארץ מצרים” (ostensibly the *Land of Egypt*). The context repeatedly plays on the themes of slavery and death, which is present in Akkadian “*mēsīrum*” (*imprisonment*), “*mēšīrum*” (*a magical drawing made to ritually counteract evil*) and “*māt Mušri*” (*Land of Egypt/Death Neighbor*). The base form “*ešēru*” can signify to “to *prescribe death*” as a punishment. It is expressed with the logogram “*ḪUR*”, which “*MAT*” and “*KUR*”—designating a foreign land (CAD, CDA, CSL, Str).

positing translation from cuneiform as “*preposterous to an Assyriologist*”—without identifying the proposals or providing any reasons for this blanket condemnation (p. 113).

Albright (and most of his colleagues) assumed the oral transmission of myths borrowed by the Hebrews from neighboring civilizations in antiquity. During his long and influential career, Albright maintained that the accounts of Genesis were originally recited in “*Patriarchal Hebrew*” and then recorded in “*demythologized*” format in the 7th century BC (Albright 1968: pp. 50-51, 92, 184-85). His analysis follows the biblical timeline while incorporating the discoveries of ancient myths and the modern recognition that the biblical accounts were written long after the eras of the narrative. The influence of this conception of oral history followed by written work appears to be one of the factors that caused the cuneiform hypothesis to fade from scholarly view.

Perhaps more than anything else, the emergence of the Documentary Hypothesis in the late 1800s as the new paradigm for understanding the “Old Testament” silenced other voices with its own din. Its dominance resulted in a failure to consider a much more direct explanation for the anomalies of the Hebrew text: namely, that Albright’s “*Patriarchal Hebrew*” might in fact be a Hebrew translation of Akkadian. The Documentary Hypothesis came into vogue at the same time that cuneiform tablets containing the Mesopotamian flood narratives were being discovered and translated. In a bizarre quirk of history, the advocates of this hypothesis adopted Noah’s Ark as the proof text for the existence of multiple indigenous Hebrew folklore traditions that were combined into one account:

The resolution of the compound narrative [of the Genesis flood account] into its constituent elements...is justly reckoned amongst the most brilliant achievements of purely literary criticism, and affords a particularly instructive lesson in the art of documentary analysis. Skinner, 1910, p. 147

A century later, mainstream scholars continue to teach that the tale of Noah’s Ark is an ungainly hybrid creature created by an inept literary gene-splicer:

The prevailing opinion views the Flood narrative as the work of an editor who conflated two accounts into one. The repetitions (e.g. Gen. 6:5-8//6:9-13), contradictions (Gen. 6:19-20 versus 7:2) and redundancies (e.g. Gen. 7:77//7:13; 7:17//7:18) are indeed unmistakable. Van der Toorn, 2007, p. 140

Critics of this approach note that the perception of “*contradictions*” is at odds with the idea of a combining editor who would certainly have noticed his own restatements of key clauses (Clines, 2013). If the editor perceived no disharmony between the repetitions he was responsible for, why should western scholars project their modern distaste for redundancy

upon a story from another time, place and culture? How could a formulation guided by anachronistic logic become a widely accepted theory?

A quick glance at one of the oldest known Ark accounts (written in Sumerian cuneiform) reveals an abundance of repetitions and redundancies:

All the windstorms and gales arose together, and the flood swept over...After the flood had swept over the land, and waves and windstorms had rocked the huge boat...Utu the sun god came out, illuminating heaven and earth...the hero Utu entered the huge boat with his rays. ETCSL 1.7.5, D:1-8, Gábor Zólyomi translation

Repetition and chiasmus are hallmarks of ancient Near Eastern literature. Aside from the aesthetic qualities of poetic parallel, the scribal restatement of phrases in alternate form serves to clarify the meaning of cuneiform texts that inherently possess the potential to be read several different ways. The semantic value of repetition holds true for consonantal texts lacking capitalization, punctuation and standardized letter spacing. Moreover, repetition is a property of liturgical works, while arcane word manipulations are intrinsic to magical texts. Both of these are among the genre possibilities that must be considered if the original *context-of-use* is to be understood.

Although this rebuttal does not exclude the hand of a late editor, it undermines a pillar of source critical methodology—the idea that redundancy is a literary defect that establishes the existence of rival literary traditions. The problem is not the postulation of the existence of older sources—which the narrative itself implicitly admits (i.e. Gen. 1:21, cf. Ps. 74:12-14; Gen. 6:4, 10:8-9). Rather, the issues begin with mistaking repetition and iteration for separate sources. These are interpreted as evidence of a lack of literary skill and creative purpose on the part of the scribes. These errors are compounded by incorrect assumptions regarding the date, religion, language and mode of transmission. Finally, the hypothesis itself is taken as an unquestionable framework into which all data must be shoehorned.

As a consequence, recent inclusion of the Mesopotamian flood accounts in source analysis has not yielded new insights. John Day (2013) asked whether “*an ancient Near Eastern text may actually have been a source lying behind what we find in the Old Testament*” (p. 74). However, Day’s analytical starting point (p. 77) assumes the “widely accepted” presence of two Hebrew flood traditions—one featuring “*Elohim*” (E), the other “*Yahweh*” (J). This confounds the Mesopotamian origin of the story with conjectural notions of pre-exilic Israelite religion. Day perceives a monotheistic retelling of a Mesopotamian story that was “*originally mediated to the Israelites through the Canaanites*”—and recorded in Hebrew written form around 800 BC (p. 84). It simply counts the Mesopotamian flood stories as sources that should be included in the unchanged prevailing hypothesis.

The potential value of studying the Mesopotamian literary templates used to construct the Genesis Ark account is neutered by continued reliance upon the assumptions of the classic J, E and P sources of the Documentary Hypothesis (Kraeling, 1923; Day, 2013; Harper, 2021). These include the idea that the Jewish contribution to the evolution of theology is monotheism, which is often qualified as “*ethical*”. This suggests that the earlier stories and their deities had no ethics or morals, which is simply not true. The Mesopotamian flood revolves around the conflict between the beneficent creator Éa and the evil Enlil. As for pre-exilic Israelite monotheism, its existence is challenged by abundant archaeological evidence of polytheism—supported by many references to polytheistic practices and beliefs in the Hebrew scriptures (Dever, 2005, p. 252 *ff*; Adler, 2022). The scholarly preoccupation with proving and sustaining the J-E-P framework has come at the cost of understanding the meaning and the purpose of retelling multiple Mesopotamian myths in Genesis (Clines, 2013).

There is one more critical point to add to this topic. The source analyses rely on a supposition that may seem too obvious to challenge: the presence of one Hebrew god known by two different names. If the Hebraic flood narrative derives from older Mesopotamian accounts, the presence of multiple gods (as opposed to multiple sources) may well carry over from the original. This raises the possibility that the dual divine names in Genesis (especially Gen. 1 vs. Gen. 2) initially represented two Mesopotamian gods (acting collaboratively) rather than two ancient Hebrew sources (see section 7 below).

4. Double Meanings

The similarities between the flood account of Genesis and the older Mesopotamian versions are too great to be coincidental. The simplest and most direct explanation is that the account in Genesis is a reworking of the Mesopotamian story. Nevertheless, the Hebraic Ark account is incorporated into the history of the nation. Noah (the Hebraic form of the Mesopotamian ark builder) became the ancestor Abraham, Isaac and Jacob, the patriarchs of Israel. This alerts us to the likelihood that the changes made to the Mesopotamian account have a direct application to the tribes of Israel.

As noted above, the Genesis account employs a word for the rescuing watercraft that does not occur in the Sumerian or Akkadian versions. Once again, the only other appearance of this word (תבה < *tabû*) is in the story of the basket that miraculously preserved the infant Moses—who then brought the 12 (*TAB.U*) tribes out of bondage. In this context, the word was chosen to invoke the rise (*tabû*) of the captive nation that would otherwise sink, drown or be submerged (*ṭabā'u*).^{2,7} This reversal cancels their debt (*ṭabbu'u*) recorded on a tablet.² It pleads for the survival in the midst of a cataclysmic storm.

This cuneiform-based vocabulary extends throughout the Genesis description of the Ark. It is also found in the name and identity of Noah himself, as we shall see. The complex and ingenious wordplay of the Genesis Ark account attests to written composition in cuneiform. It is not a product of Hebrew oral tradition. Neither is it the written residue of a dim-witted editor. Nor does it preserve “*Patriarchal Hebrew*” from the 2nd millennium BC. Instead, the narrative appears to be written in the medium in which the scribes encountered it.

To better understand their selection of Akkadian words and logograms, we need to briefly review the potential of cuneiform signs and phrases to express double and triple meanings. The cuneiform writing system began as pictographs that were combined to form sequences (Falkenstein, 1936). The initial communication mode was visual. However, each figure also carried the name of the object depicted, offering the potential for audial use. Early pictographic “sentences” evolved to express the literal sound of the language by using the names of the pictographs as syllables (Deimel, 1922). This expansion eventually produced a polyvalent writing system in which any given cuneiform sign could represent either a sound value (syllabogram) or an idea (logogram). Over time, cuneiform retained both properties, allowing the written language to “*communicate aurally on one register and visually on another*” (Noegel, 2021).

This twin system expanded exponentially via a second (overlapping) duality. Cuneiform was invented by the Sumerians, who used it to express their language. It was then borrowed by the Akkadians, who employed the same symbols to represent their own tongue. This means that Akkadian texts have the capacity to simultaneously express Sumerian motifs retained in the signs. This duality is reflected in many terms for “*word craft*” in the Akkadian lexicon—including “*lumāšu*” (*twin-image*), “*amāt niširti*” (*hidden word*) and “*niširti ummâni*” (*secret lore of the scholars*), among others (Landsberger and Kinniar Wilson, 1961; McHugh, 2017).^{7,2} The scholarly mastery of multiple meanings of cuneiform signs and phrases was understood as mastery of esoteric knowledge (McHugh, 2017).

A key aspect of cryptic cuneiform writing is the existence of hidden words or ideas that did not need to be written. These could be signaled by semiotic linkage to the unwritten facet or factor. As explained by Avigdor Hurowitz,

Word play...can be employed for emphasis or illusion, infusing the text with connotations above and beyond the plain, simplest, surface level meaning expressed by the individual words, their grammar and syntax...they may be external or intertextual, employing a word in the text and invoking another that is not found explicitly in the text but will be brought to mind by the reader or listener. In other words, an author may play upon a word he has written, or upon a word that he has not written but that he expects the reader to know and quickly recall. Hurowitz, 2000, pp. 63-64

This scribal art manifests in all known versions of the Mesopotamian flood story. In the Akkadian accounts, it begins with the fury of the god Enlil over the turmoil and clamor of the earth's inhabitants. This noise is referred to as "*ḥabāru*", which in feminine stative form is "*abrat*"—signaling "*humanity*" (*abrātum*).⁷ The homophone "*abāru*" means "*to accuse someone*" or "*denounce*" them.⁷ This alerts us to the presence of a path strewn with double-entendres, wending its way through the narrative that follows.

Enlil decided to utterly destroy man and beast. His rival Éa (Sumerian Enki), the creator of life, was determined to ensure the survival of his creatures. However, Enlil and the Divine Council bound Éa and his allies by oath, forbidding them to intervene in the holocaust decreed from on high. Enlil's decree constituted a horrifically one-sided Prime Directive against divine interference in human affairs. The gods could destroy but were not allowed to save. The contextual purpose of the complex wordplay in the Mesopotamian ark stories is therefore to circumvent this edict—while still following the letter of the law.

The oldest known form of the story (2300-1600 BC) is referred to as "*Eridu Genesis*" or the "*Sumerian Deluge Myth*". Enki, the wisest and cleverest of the gods, came up with a plan to get around the Prime Directive. Instead of speaking directly to the protagonist Ziusura, Enki spoke to the reed wall of his house in a dream, warning the pious hero of the coming flood. This double-blind strategy in the plot is mirrored by the scribe's choice of particular cuneiform signs to convey Enki's warning:

Cuneiform transcription (ETCSL 1.7.4)¹⁶

iz-zi-da a₂ gab₂-bu-ĝu₁₀ gub-ba [...]iz-zi-da inim ga-
ra-ab-dug₄ inim-[ĝu₁₀ he₂-dab₅]

English translation (Gábor Zólyomi)

Side-wall standing at my left side...Side-wall, I
will speak words to you.

Sumerian "*iz-zi*" means "*house wall*", "*flood*" and "*waves*".³ The final syllable "*da*" functions as a comitative suffix while also signifying "*to protect*" and "*nearness*".³ It is linked to "*a₂*", which means "*side*", "*power*" and "*time*".¹⁴ Enki's words thereby convey a warning of the flood while appearing completely innocuous on the surface. The phrase "*a₂ gab₂-bu-ĝu₁₀*" (*my left side*) signals oblique speech, alerting the dreamer to a hidden meaning. "*Gub*" means "*to be assigned to a task*" (Akk. *izuzzu*).¹⁴ It is addressed simultaneously to the reed wall (which will be repurposed to build the boat) and to Ziusura, who is divinely summoned to serve as "*(i)Gub-ba*" (*ecstatic, prophet of a particular god*).^{2,7}

In both Babylonian and biblical thought, the default direction of orientation is east. This is retained in modern Hebrew, where "*forward*" (קדימה) is "*eastward*" (קדמה). Enki's speech is addressed to the wall on his left while facing forward. This means that the cardinal direction

¹⁶ Electronic Text Corpus of Sumerian Literature (ETCSL)—Black et al. 2006.

indicated by Enki's left hand is north (Akk. *šapunu*). Semitic “špn” (שפן) connotes “hidden”.¹⁷ Enki's stance is thus a stage orientation that identifies everything that follows as hidden knowledge (banned by the Prime Directive).

Four lines below, the Sumerian warning specifies that an “*a-ma-ru*” (*flood*) will sweep over. This word carries the additional Akkadian double-meanings of “*side wall*” and “*to dream a dream*”.⁷ The boat is described as “*gur₄.gur₄*”, which is translated as “*huge*” (ETCSL t.1.7.4). However, the logogram “*GUR₄*” (LAGAB) represents Akkadian “*kutlu*”—“*side-wall*”.⁷ The doubled form “*GUR₄.GUR₄*” (*NIGIN*) represents Akkadian “*saḥāru*”, which invokes the turning of divine favor on behalf of a supplicant.^{2,7} In Sumerian, “*nigin*” means “*to halt, turn away*” (wrath) and “*to assemble, to pen up cattle*”.³

Thus, all the props in this play function as puns intrinsic to the plot and designed to skirt the Prime Directive. The cuneiform signs are words of power spoken by the rescuing god—as conceived by the authoring scribe. In this sense, the clever scribe became the ally of ingenious Enki in defeating the evil scheme of Enlil.^{2,7} This is a critical point with regard to the later Judean retelling of the story.

Even though the account is in Sumerian, it was written during the Sargonic era under the Akkadian Empire (or perhaps later). The scribe was fluent in both Sumerian and Akkadian. A millennium later, a different scribe used a similar set of double-entendres in the version of the story that appears in the Epic of Gilgamesh. The eponymous hero met Utnapištim (another name for the builder of the ark) who recounted the saga of the flood. As in the earlier iterations of the story, Enki (now called Éa) addressed the wall of the protagonist's home in a dream (Gilg. XI:21):

<u>Cuneiform transcription</u>	<u>English translation (A.R. George, 1999 p. 89)</u>
Ki-ik-kiš ki-ik-kiš i-gar i-gar	O fence of reed! O wall of brick!

These syllables spell out the Akkadian words “*Kikkišu, kikkišu, Igāru, igāru*” (*Reed fence, reed fence, Wall, wall*). However, each sign retains its original Sumerian sense, revealing another level of meaning. Thus, the logogram “*KI*” signifies “*earth*” while the Akkadian preposition “*ki*” indicates “*for*”.^{3,7} “*IK*” (as *GAL₂*) means “*to guard, protect*”, “*take an oath*” and assign a “*task*” (Akk. *bašû*, cf. Sum. *gub*).^{3,7,14} “*KIŠ*” represents the “*world*” and “*totality*”, while the Akkadian form “*kiššatu*” also describes a river at “*full flood*” stage.^{7,14} Just as in the Sumerian account, the beneficent creator warns of the flood to come while signaling that he has a plan to save life from this disaster.

¹⁷ This concept appears in the story of the infant Moses, whose person and purpose were concealed (תצפנהו—*tšpnhw*) in his ark (Exod. 2:2-3).

Éa then instructed Utnapištim to build a boat using reed bundles (*kiššu*) cannibalized from his house.¹⁸ The boat was thereby built of elements of inhering symbolic power, ensuring the survival of the people and animals within. The logogram for boat (^{giš}MA₂) represents its Akkadian equivalent, “*eleppu*”. However, the homophone “*elēpu*” means to “*increase, multiply*” descendants.⁷ Once again, the clever scribe became the understudy of wise Éa, helping him to save both the pious hero and people of his native city.

Another version (written between the Sargonid and Gilgamesh accounts) gives the craft an Akkadian proper name. Written in Nippur in the Middle Babylonian Period (CBS 13532), the account identifies the boat as the “*Naširat Napištim*” (Lambert and Millard, 1969). It literally means “*Preserver of Life*”.¹⁹ It appears as another step in the series beginning with Sumerian “^{giš}MA₂.NIGIN”, which is Akkadian “*Eleppu Saḫāru*”—“*Boat of Turning Divine Favor*”.

The logogram for “*napištu*” is “ZI”, which connects the Hebraic ark (תבה = *tbh* < *tabû* = *ZI*) to its Mesopotamian predecessors. Each iteration of the story revolves around this logogram, which forms the root of the names of the original protagonist (*Ziudsura*) and his successor (*Utnapištim* = ^(d)*Utu.ZI*). The theme of the devastation, survival and renewal of life lies at the heart of the myth. The shared cuneiform logographic symbolism between the Genesis account and its predecessors points to a common written (rather than oral) tradition.

5. The Two-word Name of Noah's Ark

These linguistic roots demonstrate that the Genesis Ark story is a written adaptation of earlier Mesopotamian accounts. This literary origin suggests that we should look for a two-word Hebraic ark name, following the pattern of “*Naširat Napištim*”. Significantly, Noah did not build “*an ark*”—he built “*The Ark*”. The Hebrew text uses the definite article “ה” (*ha*) in 25 out of 28 occurrences of the craft's name.²⁰ Of the three remaining occurrences, one is in construct state while others are preceded by the prepositions “ל” (*la*) and “ב” (*ba*)—which subsume the definite article.

Given that Akkadian lacks the Hebrew definite article that we see in “התבה” (*ha-tebah*), it raises the possibility that the prefix “ה” (*ha*) is a transcription of a cuneiform sign that belongs to the watercraft's name. Over the course of Mesopotamian history and language evolution, six different cuneiform signs were used to represent the sound “*ha*”.¹² The Neo-Assyrian sign

¹⁸ The homophone “*kiššu*” means “*shrine, chapel*” (ePSD). As the priest of Éa, Atrahāsis was told to build a floating sanctuary for his patron god, adding another level of protection. Holloway (1998) notes that the Sumerian dimensions and description of the Ark correspond to a ziggurat—the traditional tiered pyramidal temples of Mesopotamia.

¹⁹ Foster (2005) translates “*Guardian of Life*”. Lambert and Millard (1969) render it “*Life Saver*”.

²⁰ Strong's Exhaustive Concordance of the Bible (Str)—Strong J (2005).

“𐎶” (HA₄) is also “ŠAR₂”, representing “*kiššatu*”—which again means “*totality, world*” and “*full flood*”.^{7,12} It evokes (via homophony) the reed bundles (*kiššu*) of the reed wall (*kikkišu*) that was repurposed to build the Akkadian ark.

The same symbol “𐎶” (as *dug₃*) means “*sweet, good, favorable*” in Sumerian.³ The Akkadian synonym is “*ṭābu*” (Heb. טֹב—*ṭob*).¹⁴ It is a homophone of the Neo-Babylonian pronunciation of “𐎶𐎵” (ZI) as “*tabû*”. This gives us “*Tabû Ṭābu*” (𐎶𐎵𐎶) as the 6th century name of Noah's Ark.²¹ The alliterative form of the ship's name follows the template of the “*Naširat Napištim*”. Assuming that this reconstruction is correct, it suggests that a post-exilic Hebrew translator read the cuneiform phrase “𐎶𐎵𐎶” as “*ḥa₄-ZI*” (*ha-Tebah*) rather than “*DUG₃.ZI*” (תִּבְהָ טֹב—*Tebah Ṭob*).

On a benign and disarming level, the cuneiform name given in Genesis to the vessel that sheltered all creatures from the storm can be understood “*All Life*” (ŠAR₂.ZI), “*Good Life*” and “*Favorable to Life*” (DUG₃.ZI). Underneath this charming exterior is the stunning invocation, “(May) All rise up, revolt and depart!” (ŠAR₂.ZI = *Kiššatu Tabû*).²² Since “*tabû*” is also the number twelve (TAB.U), the hidden message calls for the uprising of the tribes of Israel. The name of the watercraft (of both Noah and Moses) takes on a powerful allegorical dimension with the realization that the supreme title of the king of Babylon was “*Šar Kiššatu*” (*Lord of All*, which can also be read as *Lord of the Flood*)—making him the target of the 6th century words of overthrow and escape.²³

In many English translations, the arks of Noah and Moses are not thematically connected due to different renderings of “תִּבְהָ” in what are perceived as two different contexts (*ark* vs. *basket*). In fact, the two are archetypically the same vessel (Fig. 1). The twin accounts tell two sides of the same story. Moses was hidden in his ark to save him from Pharaoh's destruction of the Hebrews. Moses subsequently led the revolt and the escape that is foretold by the name of his craft. Noah's Ark calls for the same rescue through the watery deep—but with different nuances. The setting of both is the Babylonian exile:

The sea is come up upon Babylon: she is covered with the multitude of the waves thereof... My people, go ye out of the midst of her. Jer. 51:42, 45 KJV

²¹ The order of words is reversed in the transition from logogram to Akkadian (cf. *Apsû < ZU.AB*).

²² Sumerian “*ḥa*” can function as an affirmative prefix signifying “*may, let, indeed*” (SL).

²³ “*ḤA₄*” (𐎶) is the “*tenû*” form of “*GAR*” (𐎶)—tilted to the left. Sumerian “*gar*” signifies “*form, appearance*”, “*to deliver, establish, restore*” and “*to remove and set elsewhere*” (SL). This symbolic shift is present in the logogram “*ḤI.GAR*” (𐎶𐎶), which signifies “*revolt, rebellion*” (Akk. *bārtu*—CDA). Hence, “𐎶” activates the deliverance and restoration of the Life (ZI) of the 12 tribes (TAB.U) that follow, corresponding to Éa's “*left-hand*” plan in the Akkadian template.

The Mesopotamian Arks, their Heroes and their Gods: A Logographic Progression

The Heroes	The Boats		The Gods
<p>Ziudsura Mng: Life of Lasting Days (He of) Long Ago and Far away Logogram: ZI.UD.SU₃.RA₂ Logo. Mngs: Life.Storm.To Drown Life.Sun.To Rejoice</p>	<p>Materials: Side-wall of house Sum. iz-zi-da Sum. Dbl. Mng: A flood is near Flood-to protect Akk. Mng: To be assigned a task (izuzzu)</p>	<p>Sumerian (2300-1600 BC) note: Akkadian era archaism</p> <p>Shape: Round Significance: Apotropaic Circle? Name: ⁸¹⁵ma₂.gur₄.gur₄ Akk. Nm: Eleppu Kutlati, Saḥāru Logogram: MA₂.NIGIN Mng: Huge Boat, Circular Boat Boat of Side-wall.Side-wall Boat of Assembly Boat of Turning Divine Favor Source: Eridu Genesis Ref: ETCSL 1.7.4</p>	<p>Evil: Enlil (king), An (sky), Sud (submersion) Good: Enki (creator of life), Utu (sun), Inanna (Venus)</p>
<p>Atra-ḫasīs Mng: Very Wise Excellent Plan Good Liver Omen Logogram: SI.A.GEŠTUG DIRI.GEŠTUG Logo. Mngs: Inundate.Water.Hear To completely still. Water.Think of; Reed-raft.To make wide</p>	<p>Materials: Reed wall of house Akk. kikkišu Logogram: KI.IK.KIŠ KI.GAL₂.KIŠ Logo. Mngs: Place.To Put.All Place.To Protect.All For.Task.Full Flood</p>	<p>Akkadian (1800-1400 BC)</p> <p>Shape: Round Significance: Totality, Moon Name: Naširat Napištim Logogram: UR₃.ZI (~ ^dŠEŠ.ZI) Mng: Life Saver Guardian of Life Life Protected (by the Moon) Sources: Ark Tablet Nippur Tablet Ref: Irving Finkel, 2014 Lambert & Millard, 1969</p>	<p>Evil: Enlil (king), Anu (sky), Adad (storm), Zū (wind), Ninurta (warrior), Errakal (underworld), Nintu (the betraying mother goddess), Sîn (the betraying moon) Good: Éa (creator of life), Šamaš (sun)</p>
<p>Utnapištim Mng: He Found Life Payment of Life Logogram: UD.ZI.DIM Logogr. Mngs: Storm.Life.Make Fast Sun.Life.Make Fast</p>	<p>Materials: Reed fence of house Akk. kikkišu Wall of house Akk. igāru Akk.Dbl.Mng: Side of a ship</p>	<p>Akkadian (1300-700 BC)</p> <p>Shape: Pyramidal (truncated) Stepped Ziggurat (eq. L, W, H: 7 levels) Significance: Temple (É.GAL) Name: ⁸¹⁵MA₂.Elēpu (< Eleppu) Mng: Boat To Increase Descendants To Flourish Source: Gilgamesh Tablet XI Ref: Andrew George, 2003 Steven Holloway, 1998</p>	<p>Evil: Enlil (king), Anu (sky), Ninurtua (warrior), Ennugi (canals), Adad, Šullat, Haniš (storm gods), Errakal (underworld), Bēlēt-ilī (betraying mother goddess) Good: Éa (creator of life), Šamaš (sun)</p>
<p>Nōaḥ (נח) Heb. Mng: Rest Akk. Nuāḥu Akk. Mng: Calm Waters; Appease the Wrath of an Angry God Logogram: ^(lū)HUN.GA₂ Logogr. Mngs: ^(man)To Hire.nominative To Assign a Task. (to) House/Basket Constellation: the Ram Dumuzi the Shepherd</p>	<p>Materials: Reed shepherd's hut Heb. 'šy-gpr (עצי-גפר) Heb. Mng: none Akk. gapru (bīt kikkiši) Logogram: ⁸¹⁵GUB.RU Logogr. Mngs: Assigned task.To restore Sealant (waterproofing) Heb. kpr (כפר) Heb. Mng: atonement Akk. kupru, Sum. é-a Akk. Mng: bitumen Logogr. Mng: ^dÉa's purification</p> <p>Shape: Oblong or Rect. Prism Significance: Apotropaic Heb. Name: Ha-Tebah (התבה) Heb. Mng: none Akk. Name: Tabû Ṭābu Akk. Mng: Favorable for Setting out, departing, rising up, revolting Logograms: Tabû ZI Tabû I.ZI.A Tabû TAB.U (2.10) Tabû Ṭābu ḤA₄.ZI (DUG₃.ZI, ŠAR₂.ZI, LIMMU-tēnû.ZI) Logogr. Mngs: Life Lead Out Life (from) Water Twelve (12) Favorable for Life, All Life Change the Anihilation of #4 (4/12: Judah/Tammuz) Sources: Genesis 6:5-9:29 Exodus 2:1-3, 3:14, 8:20 Isaiah 18:2, 35:7</p>	<p>Evil: Marduk (^d50), Sîn (^d30), Adad (^d10) Good: Éa (^d40), Dumuzi (shepherd), Tiranna (rainbow), Šamaš (šamšatu: AŠ₄.ME = 600) Both: Yahweh?</p>	
<p>Mōšeh (משה) Heb. Mng: Draw Out Akk. Mu-šēḫu, Mušēḫû Akk. Mng: Rebel, Son who Rises Up and Revolts; One who Disputes a contract</p>	<p>Materials: Bulrushes, cumin (wordplay) Heb. gm' (גמ), Akk. kamû'u, Sum. gamun Logograms: TIN.TIR, ^uTIN.TIR^{ki}, TIN.TIR.MA₄, GAM, GAM₃, GAM₄ (DUMU) Logogr. Mngs: Wood of Life, Babylon plant, Babylon.To depart; Circle, Watch over, Son, Shepherd's crook, To throw down Akk. kamû (LAL): Capture; God held captive in the underworld; To capture capturers, To bind enemy land, god</p>	<p>Shape: Round Significance: Apotropaic Heb. Name: Ha-Tebah (התבה) Heb. Mng: none Akk. Name: Tabû Ṭābu Akk. Mng: Favorable for Setting out, departing, rising up, revolting Logograms: Tabû ZI Tabû I.ZI.A Tabû TAB.U (2.10) Tabû Ṭābu ḤA₄.ZI (DUG₃.ZI, ŠAR₂.ZI, LIMMU-tēnû.ZI) Logogr. Mngs: Life Lead Out Life (from) Water Twelve (12) Favorable for Life, All Life Change the Anihilation of #4 (4/12: Judah/Tammuz) Sources: Genesis 6:5-9:29 Exodus 2:1-3, 3:14, 8:20 Isaiah 18:2, 35:7</p>	<p>Evil: Gods of "Egypt" (Chthonic Māt Mušri, Land of Death); Alammuš (^dLAL₃), serpent god of underworld, vizier of Sîn Good: Éa (אהיה), Yahweh (יהוה)</p>

Tabû Ṭābu:

- 𐎠𐎢𐎽𐎢𐏁 (NB: ḤA₄.ZI)
- 𐎠𐎢𐎽𐎢𐏁 (NB: ŠAR₂.ZI)
- 𐎠𐎢𐎽𐎢𐏁 (OB: ḤA₄.ZI)
- 𐎠𐎢𐎽𐎢𐏁 (OB: ŠAR₂.ZI)

Photo credits: Voices for Iraq: <https://voicesforiraq.org/2023/05/> References: CAD, CDA, ePSD, SL, CSL NB: Neo-Babylonian, OB: Old Babylonian N. Maranz

Figure 1. Material, linguistic and thematic interrelationships of the succession of arks in the Mesopotamian flood tradition. The (written) word choices are shaped by the interchange between paired Akkadian/Sumerian and syllabic/logographic meanings. The arks of Noah and Moses are an integral part of this tradition—but are adapted for the exilic circumstances of Judah and Israel in the mid-6th century BC.

6. Atrahāsīs Invokes the Wrong Protective God

The Sumerian and Akkadian accounts describe the involvement of many gods in the drama of the Deluge. In contrast, the Hebrew account names only “אלהים” (Elohim) and “יהוה” (Yahweh). In the Judeo-Christian tradition, they are different terms for the same god. Nevertheless, Genesis alludes to the presence of a plurality of deities (cf. Gen. 1:26, 3:22, 11:27). Although the other gods are hidden in the Hebrew text, they are visible in the reconstructed Akkadian. They include both good and evil gods.

The narrative presence of an evil deity in Genesis is signaled by the great difficulty experienced by the patriarchal clan in separating itself from the civilization of Ur—which was the ancient abode of the Sumerian moon god Nanna (Akk. *Sîn*). Instead of journeying to the Land of Canaan as intended, they instead settled in Harran—the sister city of *Sîn* in northwestern Mesopotamia (Gen. 11:31). Although the nature of the link between these two cities is not explicitly established in the narrative, the clan's move from one to the other discloses strong ties to the moon god cult. The deity of Adam, Noah and his son Shem—who did not belong to Harran or its family of gods—then rejoins the narrative.²⁴ He instructed Abram to resume the clan's westward migration (Gen. 12:1). The interrupted journey suggests that the moon god had a cultic hold on the future nation of Israel that was exceedingly difficult to break (cf. Gen. 31:19-30, 35:4).

The patron god of these two cities of bondage is therefore central to the Hebraic narrative. The moon god's name appears in the Hebrew phrase, “אור כשדים” —“*Ur of the Chaldees*” (Gen. 11:28). The word “אור” (*Ur*) in Genesis transcribes cuneiform “*URU₃^{ki}*”—the “*Place of Light*”. The moon god was called “*dURU₃^{ki}*” (*god Light^{place}*), making him synonymous with the city. “*Uru₃*” is a Sumerian term for a “*glowing, luminous object*”.^{3,25} It also signifies “*watch fire*”, invoking his divine protection upon the city.³ The custom of naming a city for its patron god (or vice-versa) was common in antiquity (Roberts, 1972, pp. 58-59). Ur is a prominent example. To understand the moon god's cryptic presence in Genesis, we need to take a close look at his role in the Mesopotamian myth that the Judean scribes selected as a template for retelling their own story.

The moon god makes a brief appearance in the Akkadian flood account—ostensibly as a protective deity. However, it becomes clear that he is a fraud. Instead of guarding life, *Sîn* is revealed to be a member of the evil majority of gods seeking the annihilation of life. Unaware

²⁴ The introduction of “יהוה” as a new deity in Exodus suggests that his presence in Genesis is an editorial artifact (cf. Exod. 6:2-3).

²⁵ The homophone “*UR₃*” (*GA₂ x NIR*) encloses the Sumerian sign for “*lord*” and “*trust*” (*nir*) within the sign for house (CSL, ePSD).

of this duplicity, the flood hero (in this case Atrahāsīs) cried out to Sîn for help in the terror of the tempest:

I went up on the roof and pr[ayed] to my lord Sin: “Let my heartbreak (?) be extinguished! [Do you not disap]pear!” ... darkness. Into my ... Sin, from his throne, swore as to annihilation and desolation on (the) darkened [day (to come)].

Ark Tablet: 45–50, Irving Finkel translation

In keeping with the ubiquitous wordplay of the cuneiform narrative, Sîn's actions turn on the meanings of his divine names. Although Sîn is referred to by his title “^dEN.ZU”, his identity as “^dURU₃^{ki}” is clearly present in the mind of the authoring scribe.²⁶ In the midst of the terrifying darkness, Atrahāsīs went to the roof (*u₂-ri*) to seek the light (*uru₃*).²⁷ However, the Sumerian homophone “*uru₂*” means “*devastating flood, thunderstorm*”, while “*ur₂*” signifies “*flood*” and “*to erase, wipe out*”.³ As the divine watch fire (*Uru₃*), Sîn initially seemed the appropriate god to call upon for deliverance. Instead, he is unmasked as a god of destruction.

The moon god's betrayal of Atrahāsīs runs deeper yet. The Akkadian ark name “*Nāširat Napištim*” (*URU₃.ZI*) invokes Sîn's protection via allusion to his logogram as a theophoric element. “*Nāširat*” is the construct state of “*našāru*”, which means “*to guard, protect, preserve*”.⁷ The word is represented logographically as “*URU₃*”.² This wordplay gives the ship's name an apotropaic aspect, calling upon the protection of moon god against the storm flood (*uru₂*).²⁸

The Akkadian Ark Tablet (line 49) cites Sîn on his throne, “^{giš}GU.ZA”. The logogram represents Akkadian “*kussû*”, which is part of the semantic field of “*kiššu*” (*strength, might*) and “*kiššatu*” (*the limitless kingdom*). In the case of the “*Nāširat Napištim*”, the throne of Sîn (*GU.ZA = GI₁₂.SA₃*) plays on “*kiššu*” (*GI.SA*), the reed material from which the ark was made. In this sense the craft physically embodied Sîn, making his betrayal of Atrahāsīs and the creatures he was trying to save all the more devastating.

²⁶ “^dEN.ZU” means “*Lord of Knowledge*”. In context, Atrahāsīs (*Very Wise*) makes a grave error since he is the priest of Éa, the true god of knowledge (*EN.ZU.AB*) who provided the plan for surviving the flood, which the hero temporarily forgets. “*Atru ḥāsīsu*” also signifies an “*excellent plan*” (and *excellent liver omen*—CDA).

²⁷ From context, Atrahāsīs went to the roof to “*pray*”—although the tablet is illegible at this point. Finkel tentatively pencils in Akkadian “*sa-ap-pi*” (*suppû*), which is expressed with the logogram “*SISKUR₂*”. In keeping with the pattern of the narrative, the missing word should instead be a form of “*erēšu*” (*URU₄*)—“*to request, to implore*” (CDA, CAD).

²⁸ Apotropaic eyes have been painted on boat prows since antiquity. The concept of the evil eye (*igi-ḥul = igi-IGI.UR*) dates back to ancient Sumer (SL, CSL). The cuneiform sign for “*eye*” (*igi*) can also represent “*life*” (*IGI = ŠI*, which interchanges with *ZI*—ePSD). The presence of “*Life*” in the logograms of the Akkadian and Hebraic arks signals a similar protective function.

7. The Judean Scribes Invoke the Right Protective Gods

The Judean scribes who wrote the flood account were clearly working from one or more Mesopotamian templates. Hence, we need to ask whether the Hebraic ark also contains apotropaic building materials in the wordplay of the text. If so, we can expect to find the theophoric elements of the protective god(s) invoked by the author(s).

Noah's water-craft was coated inside and out with "כפר" (*kpr*), which is variously translated as "pitch", "tar" or "bitumen". However, out of 102 occurrences of this word in the Hebrew Bible, this is the only context in which "כפר" signifies a waterproof coating (Str H3722).²⁰ Hence, "kpr" is clearly a transcription Akkadian "kupru" (*bitumen*), as noted by Irving Finkel (2014, p. 197). It was used in Sumer for waterproofing ships.⁷ "Kupru" is a derivative of "kapāru", which signifies both to "to wipe off" and "to smear on".²

The primary sense of "kapāru" is "to purify magically" and "to wipe clean...by ritual activity".^{2,7} This sense corresponds to the other 101 occurrences of "כפר" in the Hebrew text.²⁰ Each of these refers to atonement in some fashion, including ritual contexts such as Yom Kippur (יום הכפרים). If we connect the dots, the "כפר" coating of the Ark provided protection against divine wrath by means of the ritual purification of the passengers.

The identity of the protective deity is revealed in the Sumerian word for bitumen: "ea".¹⁴ It is written syllabically as "e₂-a", which is precisely the name of the benevolent Mesopotamian creator (^dE₂-a) who instructed Atrahāsīs to build the ark. This identification resonates with the recurrence of the number 40 in the story. The most important deities of the Mesopotamian pantheon had numbers (Black and Green, 1992). Éa's deity number is 40 (^dNIMIN), which is invoked in the 40 days and 40 nights of the storm of the Genesis account. In the earlier Mesopotamian versions, the storm lasted only seven days. This means that the Judean scribes deliberately changed it—highlighting the contextual significance of ^d40 in their adaptation of the myth.

The "kupru" that was used to waterproof the Ark of Noah can be written with the logogram "ESIR".⁷ This compound concatenates "A (LAGAB x NUMUN)"—literally "Water surrounding Box containing Seed". This is a key idea that is present in all the Ark accounts. "Seed" signifies "offspring" in both Akkadian (*zēru*) and Hebrew (זרע—*zer'a*).^{3,20} Éa (as A-a and ^dNIMIN) is synonymous with "water", "semen" and "offspring" (all of which are generative and possess conceptual plurality).³ In the story of Noah, the "kpr" coats the Ark. In Akkadian, "kupru" (as ESIR) contains seed (NUMUN). By extension, the Ark (as TAB.U = 12) contains the future offspring of Israel, matching the meaning of "MA₂" (*boat*) in the earlier accounts (Akk. *eleppu* → *elēpu*—to increase, multiply descendants).⁷

The Judean scribes conceptualized the Ark as the preserver of future generations. This is made clear in Elohim's promise at the conclusion of the Genesis account of the Flood:

And God (*Elohim*) blessed Noah and his sons, and said unto them, Be fruitful, and multiply, and replenish the earth... Behold, I establish my covenant with you, and with your seed after you. Gen. 9:1-9, KJV

The deity (*Elohim*) in the Hebrew passage ostensibly refers to Yahweh. However, the Judean scribes were working from a Mesopotamian template in which the god in question was Éa. This identification is supported by Moses' initial dialog(s) with “יהוה” (Yahweh), who appeared to him as a local god inhabiting a particular desert mountain. As such, Yahweh was unknown to the Mesopotamian patriarchs (Exod. 6:2-3). Moses himself did not know Yahweh at that point in the timeline because he was a foreign descendant of the eastern patriarchs.

This western deity subsequently identified himself with the mighty god of Mesopotamia by deriving the eastern name “אהיה” (literally *Eh-yah = É-a*) from his own name “יהוה”. In a very clever bilingual wordplay, Hebrew “*Yahweh*” is treated as the verb “*to be*” and conjugated to arrive at Akkadian “*Éa*” (Exod. 3:14).²⁹ From a narrative perspective, the Judean scribes in Babylon retroactively harmonized the two “*Yah*” gods (cf. Isa. 38:11, Exod. 15:2, Ps. 67:5 LXX “*high priest of the east*” < Ps. 68:4). This further suggests that the original divine name in Genesis was “אהיה”—which was replaced by later editors with “יהוה”.^{30,31}

The presence of a second rescuing deity in the Genesis account is signaled by the name the Judean scribes specifically chose for their version of the flood hero—“נח”. Hebrew “*Nōah*” transcribes its Akkadian cognate, “*Nuāhu*”. At first glance, the Akkadian name fittingly refers to the stilling of the waves after a storm and the appeasement of the wrath of an angry god.^{2,7}

²⁹ In Sumerian, the verb “*to be*” is “*am₃*” (A.AN)—which can double as a wordplay on “*God of Water*” (A.AN = ^dA < Éa). The scribal use of the verb “*to be*” may also connect to Hebrew “אלהים” (*Elohim*) in Genesis-Exodus. The name can be read as the title “אל הים” (*El ha-Yam*): “*God of the Sea*”. This corresponds to Éa as the deity of (fresh) water (^dIDIM) as well as “A.AN”. Hence, “אלהים” may represent a translation euphemism (in the early narratives of the Hebrew Bible) that was conceptually part of the original semantic field formulated by the Judean scribes.

³⁰ The accounts of Moses' initial encounters with “יהוה” (at the edge of the wilderness of סיני—*Sin*) inform us that the Mesopotamian patriarchs did not know this name (Exod. 6:2-3, cf. Gen. 12:1, 26:2, 31:3). This indicates that the presence of “יהוה” in the patriarchal narratives is a “תקון סופרים” (*Tikun Sofrim—Correction of the Scribes*).

³¹ According to the rules of the scribes, it was permissible to alter divine referents in order to avoid “misunderstandings”—including the presence of multiple deities (Megillah 9a:12, cf. Bereshit Rabbah 1:7, 49:7). Since these emendations were required to be subtle (JT Megillah 1:9:16), the original name would have been very similar to “יהוה” (→ Exod. 3:14).

The word appears in conjugated form in the version of the Deluge story that is recounted in the Epic of Gilgamesh:

The sea subsided (*in-nu-uh*), the destructive storm calmed, the flood ceased.

Gilg. XI:131²

At a deeper level of signification, *nuāhu* is expressed with the logogram “*ḪUN.GA₂*” — which is the name of the constellation of Dumuzi the shepherd god (Rogers, 1998).² This constellation “dwells” in the night sky during the winter rains that are characteristic of the Fertile Crescent. In late spring, it sinks below the horizon—coinciding with the onset of the long summer drought and the withering of vegetation. The constellation rises again in the fall, bringing the barren earth back to life. Dumuzi (*Tammuz*) was thus the pre-eminent deity associated with the restoration of life (Black and Green, 1992).

The identification of Noah with the divine shepherd “*ḪUN.GA₂*” is cross-referenced by the material used to build the Ark. The mysterious “עצי-גפר” (*‘šy-gpr*) is traditionally translated into English as “*gopher wood*” (Gen. 6:14, KJV). It is the only occurrence of this term in the Hebrew Bible.²⁰ Akkadian “*gupru*” (or *gubru*) refers to a “*shepherd's reed hut*”—which can also be written “*bīt kikkiši*”.² This matches the material of the Akkadian ark.³² As a one-of-a-kind word found only in this context, the direct correspondence to the source myth is very unlikely to be coincidental or an artifact of this language analysis.

Despite the striking parallels with older versions, the presentation of the usual “*kikkišu*” (*kiššu*) material in the form a shepherd's hut is a Judean innovation. Given the ubiquitous wordplay of the genre, we should expect additional layers of connected meanings. The “*gupru*” shepherd's hut is written syllabically as “*gub-ru*”.² Once again, “*gub*” signifies “*to be assigned a task*”. The logographic meaning of “*GUB.RU*” makes “*RU*” the object of “*GUB*”—in other words, the entity to whom the hidden task “*gub*” is given. “*RU*” represents Akkadian “*nadû*” —“*to throw into water*” and to “*put someone in chains*”.⁷ It is a homophone of “*nādu*” —“*to praise*”, which is the meaning of “יהודה” (*Yehudah*).³³

In the Akkadian accounts, Éa spoke to the reed wall of Atrahāsis' house and gave it instructions. He assigned the hut the task of preserving life by being formed into the Ark. In

³² Akkadian “*iš gapru*” can be read as “*superior wood*” (CDA). As an apotropaic material, “*gapru*” signifies “*to overcome*” and to “*contend, match strengths*” (cf. *gubburu*). The shepherd's hut replaces the throne of Sîn as the source of the “*kiššu*” material, juxtaposing Dumuzi and Sîn.

³³ This semantic field is present in the story of Cain (the eponymous ancestor of the Kenites), who was condemned to be a “נוד” (*nad*—*nomad*), yet settled (ישב) in the land of “נוד” (*Nod*) “קדמת-עדן” — “*before Eden*” was planted (Gen. 4:12-16, cf. Gen. 2:8, Deut. 32:10-14). In Mesopotamia, the steppe was called “*eden*”. The livestock herders who inhabited the steppe were known as “*nādu*” (*ḪUŠ*) from the leather water-skins they carried (SL, CAD).

Genesis, Elohim gives instructions to Noah (*Nuāḥu* = ^(lú)ḤUN.GA₂ = *Dumuzi*) to use his reed shepherd's hut (*gub-ru*) to build the Ark (*Tabû* < *TAB.U* = 12). The task is assigned to "RU" (*nadû* < *Nādu* = Judah). In Sumerian, "ru" means "to lead away"—making Judah responsible for saving the lives of other 11 tribes. This sets up the critical question of how captive Judah might accomplish this.

The genealogies of Genesis make Judah the 4th son of Israel, corresponding to the month of Tammuz (*Dumuzi*)—the 4th of 12 months. Judah's task is to rescue the twelve tribes via the Ark. The logogram "TAB.U" (12) is also "TAB.GIBURU" (~*Tabû Gubru* = *Ark of the Shepherd's Hut*). "GIBURU" (גיבור) signifies "hero" in the Hebrew narrative (cf. Gen. 6:4). "TAB" means "two", signaling a pair of heroes. In Akkadian, "gabāru" (*gabrû*) designates a "copy, reply", "replacement" or an "equivalent" substitute.⁷ This makes Noah (^(lú)ḤUN.GA₂) the doppelganger of Tammuz/Judah.

One of the key themes of the mythology of the shepherd god is his unjust seizure by the demons of the underworld. They bound him and dragged him down to the land of death (Inanna's Descent, ETCSL). After a terrifying ordeal, Dumuzi returned to the land of life. By incorporating the shepherd god into their retelling of the story, the Judean scribes invoked the power of Dumuzi to overcome their nation's captivity and "death". Dumuzi's phenomenal area of power was transferred to the tribe (cf. Gen. 49:24, Isa. 63:11, Ps. 77:15-20).

Although this transposition may be far beyond the pale of both orthodox religion and established textual scholarship, it follows the clear precedent of the Hebraic Eden account. In the Sumerian source story, the goddess "Nin-ti" (*Lady Rib/Lady Life*) is born from the rib of Enki in the Garden of the Gods (Enki and Ninḥuršaga, ETCSL 1.1.1).³⁴ The formation of Eve from the rib of "Adam" in Eden is a retelling of the same story. The talking serpent who tended the "Tree of Knowledge" replaces Alammuš, the underworld serpent deity who attended "dEN.ZU"—the "Lord of Knowledge" (Sîn). These substitutions indicate that the roles of the gods in the Mesopotamian myths were indeed transferred to humans (or specific animals) in the Genesis retelling.

This reveals a pattern in which pivotal ancestors in Genesis mirror specific deities in the ancient template. This in turn signals that the nature and purpose of these deities is the key to Genesis. The Judean scribes did not "replace" the source deities with humans as an act of imaginative story-telling. Rather, they "infused" each divine persona into a carefully crafted representational ancestor. The scribes sought to ritually invest their nation with the powers possessed by these divine allies.

³⁴ Delitsch (1903) noted that the creation of male and female humans in the image of God (Gen. 1:27—plural) assumes the existence of goddesses (p. 146). He also observed that "Babylonian Noah and his wife are transformed into gods" (p. 108).

8. The Judean Scribes Countermand the Enemy Gods

The “*gabrû*” (*gpr = gbr*) matter comprising Noah's Ark metaphorically alludes to a “*duplicate copy*” of an original legal document or literary tablet. “*Gabrû*” also signifies a written “*answer*”.^{2,7} This sets up the Hebraic adaptation of the myth as a reply to the original. The prominent presence of the number “40” in Genesis is centered upon the god Éa (^d40), corresponding to his protective presence in the “*e₂-a*” bitumen coating. In parallel, Dumuzi is present in the logogram of Noah and in the “*gapru*” shepherd's hut used to build the Ark. These two “good” gods act as “*opponents*” (*gabrānû*) of the gods bent upon destruction—yet the evil deities are not overtly named.

Éa is an essential member of the original cast of gods who is symbolically present in the Hebraic account as ^d40. If we can identify one of the good gods from the source account in this manner, we have to be alert to the possibility that the evil deities of the original myth may also be present in a similar symbolic fashion. In the Akkadian source story, the instigator of the Deluge was Enlil, whose deity number is “50”. He was joined by his firstborn son Sîn, the moon god, whose deity number is “30”. These divine villains lurk in the background. Their presence is more subtle than the serpent in the Garden of Eden.

Although Enlil and Sîn are not directly named as “gods” in the Hebraic account, their numerical signs appear in the dimensions of Noah's Ark. Irving Finkel (2014) noted that the Ark of Atrahāsis was round and made from reeds, making it a larger version of the indigenous “*quffa*” boats of southern Mesopotamia. Although the Ark of Moses corresponds to the *quffa* model, the Judean scribes deliberately changed the shape of Noah's Ark. Instead of being round, the length was 300 cubits, the width 50 cubits and the height 30 cubits (Gen. 6:15). The length will be addressed in the final section of this paper. Here the width and the height are the focus.

The Hebrew word for “*width*” (רחבה—*raḥbah*) corresponds to Akkadian “*raḥābu*”—“*to shake, tremble*”.⁷ It has a specific connotation of divine wrath. In this case, it alludes to the wrath of ^d50. The Hebrew term used for “*height*” (קומתה—*qumatah*, lit. “*her height*”) reconstructs as an Akkadian wordplay on “*kamītu*” (*bonds, captivity*) and “*qimmatu*” (*crest, crown*). The latter doubles as an epithet of the moon, referring to the lunar halo.² “*Kimtu*” (*kīmatu*) means “*family*”, while “*kimiltu*” describes the wrath of deities.⁷

The semantic field of the height dimension (קומה—*qomah*) contains a potential reversal of fate. Akkadian “*kamû*” (*bound*) can refer to a god held captive in the underworld, but also appears in the alliterative omen “*ka-mu-um ka-mi-šu i-ka-am-mu*”—the “*captive will capture his captors*” (YOS 10 iii:18).² “*Kamû* is represented by the logogram “*LAL*”.⁷ In Mesopotamian belief, each of the great gods had a vizier who carried out the deity's commands. Alammuš, the

serpent vizier of Sîn, is “^dLAL₃”.³⁵ His logogram signifies “priest”, “honey” and “honey plant” — with sexual overtones.^{3,14} In Eden, the serpent set the honey plant trap (^úLAL₃) that ensnared Eve (and Adam). The serpent god was one of the twin guardians of the door of heaven and the underworld—his opposite was Dumuzi (Black and Green, 1992).³⁶

In another semiotic layer, the homophone “*kummu*” means “temple”.⁷ It is represented by the logogram “É.NUN”, which can be construed (in the context of the Ark) as the temple of Enki (alluding to his home city, Eridu—NUN^{ki}).³⁷ A version of the flood story from Ugarit (RS 22.421) states that Atrahāsīs “dwelled” in the Temple of Éa (*Bīt* ^dÉa). The earlier Sumerian story recounts that Ziusura was a “*gudug*”—a priest (of Enki). The same sign represents “*šudug*”—a “reed hut for purification rites”.^{3,12} It also means “basket”.³ When we combine these details, it appears that the hero’s reed house was actually a temple dedicated to Éa. The creator then instructed the hero to dismantle his temple and use it to build the vessel that would preserve all life. This idea may also be present in Yahweh’s instructions to Noah. The entry of all his “house” (בית—Akk. *bītu*) into the Ark (Gen. 7:1) can be read as a wordplay signaling that his “temple” was to become the vessel (כל-בביתך/אל-התבה).

The apotropaic reuse of Éa’s temple to build the Ark coexists in tension with the name given to the vessel. As discussed earlier, “*Nāširat Napištim*” (URU₃.ZI) invokes the protection of Sîn (^dURU₃^{ki}), which is underscored by Atrahāsīs’ appeal to the moon god in the midst of the storm. The conflict between these two deities reappears in the details of Noah’s Ark. The height dimension (קומה) names the number of Sîn while invoking the temple of Éa—which is underscored by the “*gupru*” (*éa*) that coated the vessel inside (מבית—*mbyt*) and out. With this understanding in mind, the Hebrew definite article “ה” (*ha*) in “התבה” (*Ha-Tebah*) may be reconstructed as cuneiform “*HA₂*” (𐎶) instead of “*HA₄*” (𐎶). “*HA₂*” is also “*I₃.A*”—which can be read as either “Éa” or “Yah”.³⁸ It gives us “*I₃-a ZI*” (*Éa Life*) as the sign of Noah’s Ark. The scribes thereby countermanded the actions of ^d50 and ^d30.

Readers trying to follow the twists and turns of this cryptic text may again raise the question of why these two enemy deities had to be hidden in the apotropaic dimensions of Noah’s Ark. Wouldn’t it have been much simpler if the Judean scribes just named them? Why play word

³⁵ Weidner God List—Zaia (2017).

³⁶ The ancient cult center of the serpent god Ningišzida near Ur was apparently relocated to the temple of the moon god (ORACC)—thus identifying him with Alammuš. The identities of the serpent deities and the celestial twins were fluid, varying with time, place and myth.

³⁷ If Sîn is reciprocally identified with his city as “^dURU₃^{ki}”, then Éa can be understood as “^dNUN^{ki}”.

³⁸ The sign “𐎶” (*I₃*) can also be understood as the “*tēnû*” (*substituted*) form of “*LIMMU*” (𐎶)—the number four. This sets up Tammuz (as ^d4, god of the fourth month and of Judah) and Éa (^d40) as paired protective powers (*I₃.A*). They shared the symbol of the ram, appealing to the nomadic roots of the Judean scribes.

games instead of simply telling the story? Once more, the answer lies in the place and time of writing—together with the Judean embrace of Éa's role as the clever god who repeatedly outwits the evil regime seeking the destruction of his people.

In the religion and folklore of Babylon, Enlil (who decreed death by flood) was replaced by Marduk (the patron god of Babylon). The patriotic Babylonian scribes assigned Enlil's ancient role as "*King of the Gods*" to their patron deity Marduk in their national epic, the "*Enuma Elish*". They "credited" the storm flood to Marduk (Ee VI:125). To cement this new status, Marduk was called "*Enlil Ilāni*" (*Enlil of the Gods*) and given fifty names (Ee VI:121-22, VII: 149)—making him "d50" in place of Enlil.³⁹

In contrast, the cult of Sîn underwent a decline from the moon god's heyday under Sargon the Great (c. 2300 BC). After a brief return to prominence during the revival of Sumerian culture in the Ur III period, the moon god was soon eclipsed by other deities (Black and Green, 1998). This historical trajectory radically changed during the reign of Nabonidus, the last king of the Neo-Babylonian Empire (556-539 BC). He dedicated his reign to restoring Sîn to his ancient glory. The centerpiece of his plan was the rebuilding of the ruined temples of the moon god in Ur and his native Harran (Beaulieu, 1989).

Of all the places the Hebrew patriarchal clan could have had as their points of origin, it is these two exact cities that are named in Genesis. It cannot be coincidental. Under the Neo-Babylonian rule of Nabonidus, the exiles of Judah lived under the wrath of Marduk (d50) and Sîn (d30). The presence of double-meanings derived from Neo-Babylonian word and sign forms underscores this connection. It gives us a historical timestamp for the composition of these accounts. The authors lived in Babylonia (where Marduk had adopted Enlil's persona) during the reign of the mad monarch Nabonidus (whose personal god was Sîn). The Judean scribes of the exile thus risked death if they were to openly call for the overthrow of the gods of Babylon and their nation's liberation from servitude.

Irving Finkel (2014) arrives at a 6th century composition date for the story of Noah's ark by assessing the technical challenges of reading cuneiform and writing adaptive works (pp. 335-340). Finkel observes that the biblical account of young Judean nobles who learned the language and literature of the Chaldeans during the exile describes a cuneiform scribal education program (Dan. 2:4).⁴⁰ This preparation exposed a cohort of Judeans (who each possessed exceptional literary talent) to the very myths in question. Finkel notes that scribal training included copying excerpts from the Epic of Gilgamesh and the Sargon Legend.⁴¹ The

³⁹ See Lilac (2019) for a useful spreadsheet matching cuneiform text with translations.

⁴⁰ Although the Book of Daniel gets the sequence of Babylonian and Persian kings wrong, it retains memories of the past that offer insight into the customs, social structure, integration of the exiles into Babylonian society and the possibility of upward mobility in the 6th and 5th centuries.

⁴¹ The legend describes the origin of Sargon the Great as an infant saved in a floating basket.

former contains the Ark and Flood account, while latter is adapted in the story of Moses (which is linked to Noah via the “תבה”).

The Judean student-scribes in Babylon learned that Enlil's rage was provoked by “*ḥabāru*” (*clamor*)—which sounds like “*ḥābiru*”. This Mesopotamian term served as the class designation for western nomads (which was adopted across the Fertile Crescent). The “*ḥābirum*” comprised the foreign group to which the Judeans belonged (העברים—*ha-'Ibrīm: the Hebrews*). The scribal usage of this term in Genesis and Exodus always reflects the “*etic*” point of view—the perception of the nation by the settled majority. As such, the Judean scribes narratively capture the sense of their own otherness in the eyes of their exilic hosts and captors. The variant “*ḥibrum*” signifies “*tribe*”, while “*ḥabārum*” has the additional meaning “*to cross water*”.^{2,7} We can readily see how and why the Judean scribes connected the Mesopotamian Deluge account to the divine wrath that destroyed their nation.¹⁰ The survival of the Mesopotamian flood heroes with their families inspired hope for the survival of their own Hebrew people.

The Ark account of Genesis is not a generic “*Flood Myth*”. Although it belongs to the genre of myth, the details are not mythological. They are allegorical and invocational. The Ark came to a rest upon the “הרי אררט”—the “*Mountains of Ararat*” (Gen. 8:4).^{42,43} In Hebrew, “ארור” (*'arur*) means “*cursed*” (cf. Gen. 3:17, 5:29). In Akkadian, “*arāru*” (*UR₄*) is also “*curse*”, while its homophonic partner “*arattū*” describes an “*excellent*” land.⁷ In Sumerian “*aratta*” means “*praise*”—thereby naming Judah (יהודה—*Yehudah*), home of the Judean scribes.^{14,44} “*Aratta*” is written with the logogram “*LAM x KUR.RU*”, which is also “*ŠURUPPAK₂*”—the name of the city of Atrahāsīs that was destroyed in the Deluge.¹² In other words, the Hebraic ark came to a rest in the Akkadian hero's native land—which is transposed to Judah.

When Noah was born, his father Lamech⁴⁵ named him for this future restorative role:

This same shall comfort us (ינחמנו—*ynahmenu*) concerning our work and toil of our hands, because of the ground which the LORD hath cursed (אררה—*'errah*).

Gen. 5:29, KJV

Lamech's use of “*us*” (נו) reveals that the people whose toil will be relieved reside outside the narrative, since he himself will perish in the flood—according the internal logic of the tale

⁴² One of the Sumerian signs for “*flood*” is “*uru₁₈*”, which is also “*ARARIM*” (CSL, ePSD).

⁴³ This mountainous region was known as “*Urartu*” in antiquity. The allegory is mapped onto a real geographic place chosen for double-entendre potential and retention of cogent surface meaning.

⁴⁴ Akk. “*aratta*” can be expressed as Sum. “*šū*”—“*share, portion*”. Its homophone “*su*” signifies “*to replace, restore, return*”. “*Aratta*” is equivalent to “*tanadatum*”, a form of “*nādu*”—“*to praise*”. The homophone “*nadū*” means “*to cast*” into water or prison (CAD, CDA, SL, MSL XV—DIRI IV:87).

⁴⁵ Lamech (למך) reconstructs as Akk. “*lamāḥu*” (var. *lumakku*)—“*lamentation priest*” (CDA).

(Baumgart, 1998, p. 35). As noted by Elizabeth Harper (2021), “*the authorial veil has slipped, and rather than referring to the story, the author speaks for his readers who are to be comforted by the narrative*” (p. 114). This signals that the calamity is temporally located in the audience's present—and that it involves hard labor. Noah fulfills this destiny by building the Ark (*TAB.U*), which is synonymous with the 12 tribes (*hibru*) that provoked divine wrath with their clamor (*ḥabāru*—cf. Exod. 32:17-33).

The Genesis scribes specified a date for the landing of Noah's Ark that is intimately connected to mid-6th century BC Babylon: the seventeenth day of the seventh month. The Akītu Festival of Sīn in Harran (resurrected by Nabonidus after he repatriated the statues of the moon cult) climaxed on the 17th of Tašrītu (Beaulieu, 1989, pp. 151-152; Thureau-Dangin, 1921, pp. 86-88). The 12 tribes thus landed in the midst of moon worship. However, the inversed dual meaning invokes the triumph of this righteous remnant over the curse of Ur and their return to the restored Land of Judah.

9. Reconciling the “*Evil Deed*” of Yahweh

The fundamental flaw of this reading of the account of Noah's Ark is the fact that Yahweh is given the role of the destroying deity. While the earlier Mesopotamian myths present the Deluge as a struggle of Life against Death, the Genesis retelling appears to assign Yahweh the antithetical roles of both Enlil and Éa. This incongruity runs counter to everything the ancient story stands for. How could the Judean scribes assign the “*evil deed*” of Enlil (Atraḥasīs II viii:35) to their own patron god? Or did they in fact do so?

The Hebrew text does not attempt to reconcile these two opposing values, yet they are presented side-by-side.

And the LORD (יהוה) said, I will destroy (אמחה) man whom I have created from the face of the earth; both man, and beast, and the creeping thing, and the fowls of the air; for it repenteth me (כי נחמתני) that I have made them. Gen. 6:7 KJV

The King James translation of the Hebrew phrase “כי נחמתני” (*ki niḥamti*) is based on an assumed context of regret. However, the phrase is a wordplay on “נח” (*Nōaḥ*), who embodies the restoration of the cursed land and people (Gen. 5:29). Although the series of “נח” (*nḥ*) puns function well in Hebrew (cf. Gen. 8:9, 21), the meanings are stronger in the source language. Akkadian “*nuāḥu*” means “*to be appeased, become peaceful*”.² The term is found the prayer, “*Let (the god) who became angry with me relent (li-nu-ḥa), let him who became furious with me forgive me*” (King, 1896, 7:26-27, CAD translation).

These ancient contexts show that the focus in Genesis is not the storm, which is a pre-existing narrative event that is retrospectively applied to Israel's destruction. The focus is the

deliverance of the protagonist, who represents the ruling tribe (*Noah* < *Nuāḥu* < ^{lú}HUN.GA₂ = *Tammuz* > 4/12 > *Judah*). The Ark is an essential entity in its own right, since it represents all twelve tribes (*TAB.U*). Judah is its captain.

This meaning is present in the source of the verb “אמחה” (*emḥeh*), which is translated as “*I will destroy*” in the passage quoted above (Gen. 6:7). The Hebrew consonants “*mḥh*” reconstruct as Akkadian “*maḥāḥu*”—“*to soak*” and “*to suffuse with tears or blood*”.^{2,46} It is expressed with a logogram “*DIRI*” (*SI.A*), which combines the signs for “*boat*” (*SI~MA₂*) and “*water*”.^{3,7} In Sumerian, “*diri*” describes a “*reed raft*”¹⁴ or a “*basket*”,³ corresponding to the original reed coracle of the Atraḥasīs account (and to the ark of Moses).⁴⁷ The intent to inundate is therefore countermanded by the sign of the boat in water (*SI.A*).

This idea derives from the Akkadian source myth. The element the “*atru*” in “*Atra-ḥasīs*” is represented by the logogram “*DIRI*”.⁷ In Sumerian, “*diri*” also refers to the “*amount by which credits of an account tablet exceed debits*”.¹⁴ In Genesis, the seeming act of divine destruction (מחה < *mḥh* = *DIRI*) is attenuated by this meaning. The Ark was covered inside and out with atonement (*kupru/kapāru*), which can either be “*wiped off*” (as sin) or “*smear on*” (to protect). In this sense, the Mesopotamian flood was used by Yah (Éa or Yahweh) to purify the nation from its sins and to protect it from the evil actions of its adversaries. The characters and their actions serve as ritual and magical proxies for this deliverance.

In the Epic of Atraḥasīs, the societal disposition before the flood was characterized by extreme delusion—a kind of collective madness. People abandoned their creator Éa and instead worshiped Enlil—the god who hated them and sought their annihilation. In Genesis (6:11), this perverted worship is cryptically characterized as “חמס” (*ḥms*)—which reconstructs as Akkadian “*ḥamsu*” (*mistreatment*), “*ḥimṣu*” (*wrongfully possessed*) and “*ḥamšū*” (*deformed*). These meanings are homophonically connected to “*ḥamšā*”, the number “*fifty*”—corresponding to Enlil as ^d50.⁷ The fateful change in divine allegiance that is described in Atraḥasīs (and in other myths) is referenced in the Hebraic account of generations before the flood:

אז הוחל לקרא בשם יהוה

It was then devalued to call upon the name Yahweh. Gen. 4:26⁴⁸

⁴⁶ In magical usage, “*maḥāḥu*” refers to the practice of casting an adverse spell by dissolving the clay figure of the victim in water (CAD). Since the Genesis flood story follows the Eden account, this procedure logically applies to “האדם” (*the man* ~ *Adam*) whom Yahweh previously formed from clay and placed in the garden.

⁴⁷ “*Diri*” has the additional nautical sense of a “*ford*” or “*crossing*” (ePSD).

⁴⁸ Talmudic sources interpret “הוחל” negatively, associating it with man’s deformation, corruption, rebellion or idolatry (Bereshit Rabbah 23:6-7, Shabbat 118b:3, Sifrei Devarim 43:18). Most Christian translations interpret the passage in a positive sense—hence, English texts typically state that people

The name “*Yahweh*” in this passage is substituted for “*Éa*” in the original flood story. For the statement to make cultural and narrative sense in the Mesopotamian setting, the name *Éa* must be read back in. This substitution is also present in the Hebraic retelling of the “*Babel of Tongues*” that follows (Gen. 11:1-9). In the original Sumerian account, Enki confused the language of mankind because “*the whole universe, the people in unison*” praised “*Enlil in one tongue*” (Kramer, 1968). He thereby broke up the cult of Enlil. Although the biblical narrative omits this rivalry, the veiled presence of conflict between the gods can be glimpsed in certain anecdotes (Gen. 6:4, 11:7, Ps. 82:1-2, 6-7).

After Atrahasis dreamt of the coming flood, he assembled his people and explained the crux of the conflict between the two gods:

My god [does not agree] with your god,
 Enki and [Enlil] are angry with one another...
 Since I reverence [Enki],
 [He told me] of this matter.
 I can[not] live in [your...]
 I cannot [set my feet on] the earth of Enlil.
 III I 36:42-48, Lambert and Millard translation

The Genesis retelling of this story is directed against Marduk (and *Sîn*). It is obvious that the Judean scribes could not openly name the patron god of Babylon (or of Harran, the hometown of the king). Why not simply use the name Enlil? After all, the Babylonians themselves recited the Epic of Gilgamesh—which names Enlil as the villain. The answer to our question likely lies in the conceptual framework and efficacy of proxy rituals. The story is a representational account. In Mesopotamian magic, the practitioner commonly imbued a clay figurine with the identity of the spell's target. In cuneiform magic, a character shaped by the scribe's stylus in the clay of the tablet served the same purpose. In either case, the representation had to be accurate. Calling for the overthrow of Enlil was pointless, because Marduk had already replaced him. Enlil himself was not their enemy, but rather Marduk. This means that the scribes had to use ^d50 as his proxy. Even so, the number is veiled. Why?

It points to the active use of the Hebraic version by the Judean exile community in Babylon. If the Babylonians got wind that public readings of the “myth” (in towns where they had resettled the Judeans) were directed against them, the communities would be at risk for reprisals. The authors lived in Babylonia (where Marduk had adopted Enlil's persona) during the reign of the mad monarch Nabonidus (whose personal god was *Sîn*). The Judean scribes

“*began to call upon the name of the LORD*” (KJV, ESV, NASB, NIV, RSV, etc.) at that time. This anachronistically interpolates *Yahweh* (or a sole deity) into the Mesopotamian milieu.

risked death if they were to openly invoke the overthrow of the gods of Babylon (and therefore the empire itself).

On the other hand, nothing prevented the Judeans from openly using the name Éa at the time of writing. We may infer that the Hebraic account initially featured his name. Without the plain textual presence of the Mesopotamian creator in Genesis, the elaborate derivation of “אהיה” (Éa) from “יהוה” (Yahweh) during Moses' first encounter with the national deity would otherwise be unnecessary (Exod. 3:14). It follows that the name “Éa” was replaced when most of the overtly polytheistic elements of the text were expunged much later.^{31,49} The preponderance of archaeological evidence indicates that widespread observance of the Mosaic Law emerged under Hasmonean rule in the 2nd century BC (Adler, 2022). The Judean scribes of the exile were active three centuries prior.

It is clear that the Judeans saw themselves in Atrahāsīs. They linked his god to their god. Although Yahweh appears to be both the destroyer and the rescuer in Genesis, a closer look reveals the hidden presence of ^d50—in this case Marduk. Since Babylon was the destroyer of Judah, the true “flood” was sent by this divine adversary. The re-identification of ^d50 sets up a grand reversal. The Judean scribes implicitly tapped into a critical element of the Atrahāsīs myth that is generally overlooked: Enlil ended up destroying his own worshipers while the devotees of Éa survived.⁵⁰ The Judeans substituted the family of their representational ancestor Noah for the family of Atrahāsīs. In so doing, they invoked the self-destruction of Babylon, following the ancient template.

10. The Ritual Context of the Ark Account

We are still missing the practical purpose of the Hebraic version of the Mesopotamian myth. It is very unlikely that a Judean scribe or group of scribes in Babylon rewrote the ancient account for purely literary ends. The language evidence indicates that it is a veiled allegory of

⁴⁹ Yonatan Adler (2022) cites a time series of Judean coins initially depicting animals or people (during the Persian and early Hellenistic eras) which are subsequently replaced by floral or non-living decorative images (after the Maccabean Revolt). The presence of an owl (associated with wisdom goddesses) on a Judean coin inscribed with the name of the high priest Yohanan signals that polytheism was socially and religiously accepted until at least the 4th century BC (YHD 25, Israel Numismatic Society). This kind of depiction is expressly forbidden in Deuteronomy (4:16-17)—which most textual scholars view as a late addition written in the name of Moses (Hallo, 2020, VIII). The text itself indicates that it is post-exilic (see Deut. 29:27-28).

⁵⁰ The Judean scribes named Noah as the antidote to this divine curse (Gen. 5:29). In parallel, they made him the 10th generation descendant of Adam—thereby the antidote to ^d10, the storm god Adad. Abraham, the 20th of the lineage, embodied the favorable divine verdict of ^d20—Šamaš.

their nation's exile and an invocation of their deliverance—which demands a cultural context.⁵¹ It was meant to be used—but how?

In antiquity, the fact that something was written meant that it was intended to be read aloud—including the Atrahāsis epic (Lambert and Millard, 1969). The Hebrew verb “לקרא” (*to read*) literally means “*to call (out)*” (cf. Deut. 31:11-12). Thus, an Hebraic Ark Tablet would have been chanted or sung—most likely in an established (Babylonian) cultural capacity. Once again, the question is “*In what capacity?*” To answer this, we have to first determine the context-of-use of the original account—the story that the Judean scribes borrowed.

The sequence of the Mesopotamian flood myth bears a striking resemblance to the ancient “*barû*” ritual. The rite was performed at the request of a supplicant troubled by illness, ill-fortune or an impending decision. The subject purchased a ram and hired a *barû* priest and his entourage. The officiants chanted all night long in an effort to persuade the “*gods of the night*” (the astral deities) to “*efface the evil signs*” (Reiner, 1995). The latter lurked in the liver of the living ram.

While the ram was waiting, the gods were asked to inscribe good omens in place of the evil ones. When the animal was sacrificed at daybreak, the priest “read” his liver, following standardized autopsy criteria (Lutz, 1918). The supplicant's fate was thereby revealed upon exposing the interior of the ram (as an oracular vehicle) to the light of dawn.

The scholarly literature classifies the activities of the *barû* priest as a form of “*divination*” called “*extispicy*”—the omenological examination of animal entrails.² This misleadingly implies fortune telling. The purpose was not to predict the future, but to change it (Steinkeller, 2005). The ram served as a proxy for the supplicant. It was believed that the features of the ram's liver could be transformed by the gods—for good or for ill. In other words, the supplicant's fate was not fixed, but rather malleable—until dawn arrived.

Piotr Steinkeller explains the concept as follows:

As imagined by the Babylonians, the procedure by which deities offered an insight into the future - or "established the truth" as it was known in Akkadian - resembled very closely the standard Babylonian court case, in that the person for whom the extispicy was performed assumed the role of the defendant, while his future, the subject of the inquiry, became the case that the divine tribunal was to decide. As in a real-life trial, the "case" was examined, deliberated over, and decided by the gods, with their verdict being subsequently made known in the entrails of the sacrificial lamb.

Steinkeller, 2005, pp. 13-14

⁵¹ According to Van der Toorn (2007, p. 140-141), the goal was to create a national written heritage combining Elohist and Yahwist traditions. This D.H. conclusion is oblivious to the transposition of Enki to Adam, Ninti to Eve, Dumuzi to Noah—and to the Mesopotamian setting of Genesis (and Exodus).

The *barû* ceremony always took place in darkness, beginning at nightfall and ending with the rising of the sun. Hence, the divine judge who rendered the final verdict was Šamaš the sun god. It was he who revealed the omens present in the liver. In addition, the priest invoked Adad the storm god.

This sequence can be seen in the stages of the Great Flood narrative. It begins with a description of the offense committed against the gods, followed by the darkness of the deluge and prayers offered up by the fearful “defendant”. The Ark is tossed about in the waves with its fate hanging the balance. The ordeal ends with the arrival of the sun god as the “judge”. Šamaš opened the Ark and rescued the righteous passengers from the disastrous fate represented by the storm.⁵² The story ends with animal sacrifice.

Tellingly, the instructions given to Atraḥasīs for the construction of the Ark specify that “*the sun god (^dUTU) must not see its interior*” (OB Atraḥasīs, CT 46:3i:30).² Given that the innards are revealed to Šamaš at the conclusion of the account, the initial prohibition suggests an intended parallel between the extispicy ram and the Ark. The word “*barû*” (*to inspect exta, observe omens*) is a synonym of “*amāru*” (*to observe ominous phenomena*)—expressed with the same logogram.² Šamaš therefore acts as the *barû* priest who “*sees*” into the Ark (ETCSL t1.7.4, D:3-6).

In the Genesis version, the animal sacrifice is followed by the appearance of the rainbow (Sum. *tiranna*). In Akkadian, “*tīrānu*” means “*mercy*”.⁶ The term is also part of the *barû* ritual, which concluded with the priest observing the “*tīrānu*” (Lutz, 1918, p. 78-79). In this case the term refers to the intestinal loops of the sheep, typically ranging from 10 to 20 in number.² An Old Babylonian prayer offered during the *barû* ritual contains the request, “*Tirannu ana 12 litūru*”—“*May the loops become twelve*”.² The request by the “defendant” for 12 *tīrānu* therefore suggests that the number was understood as a manifestation of divine mercy. In Mesopotamian sexagesimal mathematics (where 60 is considered the whole), 12 is the reciprocal of 5—which is “*IA₂*” (*Éa* or *Yah*). The logogram for “*reciprocal*” is “*IGI*”, which also signifies “*barû*” (*to see*) and “*amaru*” (the *destructive flood*).

Erica Reiner suggested that the *barû* ritual “*may have its origin in a mythological tale that has been lost*” (Reiner, 1995, p. 66). If there is a link between the *barû* concept and a myth, the Mesopotamian Ark account is the candidate *par excellence*. According to Lambert and Millard (1969), “*the content (of Atraḥasīs) gives the impression of having been intended for public recitation*” (p. 7). The end of the Sumerian version (vi:251-252) voices the incantation formula,

⁵² In “*Eridu Genesis*”, the protagonist (*Ziudsura*) specifically sacrificed to the sun god (ETCSL t1.7.4, D:9-11). “*Zi-ud-su₃-ra₂*” toggles between “*Life + storm + to drown*” and “*Life + sun + rejoice*” (SL).

and the ritual, the protagonist sought to overturn the evil fate decreed by the gods against him. Reiner's suggestion of the origin of the ritual in a myth is entirely appropriate—but with the caveat that the structure of the ark and flood myth itself points to the reciprocal influence of the *barû* ritual.

A parallel for the ceremonial recitation of such a “myth” is found in the public reading of the Enuma Elish by the high priest of Marduk during the Babylonian Akītu Festival of the New Year (Heidel, 1951).⁵⁶ Like the *barû* incantations, the underlying theme is the overturning of fate.

The chanting of the epic is here apparently intended as a magical aid in Marduk's deliverance from imprisonment, the precise nature of which is not clear.

Heidel (1951, p. 16)

The explanation may be found in the repeated fall and rise of Babylon coupled with the loss and restoration of the cultic statue of Marduk (in which he was transcendently present). The statue was normally stationed in the Éšagila—the great temple of Babylon. When Marduk was seized and taken to Aššur as a divine “*war captive*”, ethnic Babylonians residing in the Assyrian capital developed a cult of Marduk-in-Exile. The cult equated Marduk's capture with descent into the underworld (Langdon, 1923). Cuneiform descriptions of these rites attest to the ceremonial lamentation of the “death” of Marduk (referred to as *Bêl*):

Bêl went to the mountain (lower world). The city fell into tumult because of him and fighting within in it they made...The priests of incantation who go before him reciting an incantation, they are his people who wail before him.

VAT 9555/9538:23-2713, Langdon translation

Marduk's statue was carried off to the lands of Babylon's conquerors and repatriated multiple times. The Babylonian priests and scribes navigated these vicissitudes of fate by incorporating elements of the mythology of Dumuzi the shepherd, who seasonally returned from the underworld (Black and Green, 1992). By syncretizing Marduk with Dumuzi, the Babylonians transformed Marduk's “death” into life. The priests magically reversed Marduk's descent to the underworld by tapping into the shepherd god's phenomenal area of power—his inexorable return to life. The death and resurrection of Marduk (as the patron god of Babylon) implicitly mirrored the fate of the nation.

⁵⁶ Interestingly, Utnapištim indicates that the Akītu (without identifying which god it was in honor of) was celebrated during his construction of the Ark (Gilg XI:75). Since the inhabitants of Šurappak worshiped Enlil in the lead-up to the flood, it was likely his Akītu.

The Judean exiles were faced with their own dire circumstance of conquest and deportation. Although Yahweh did not have a cult statue (as far as we know), the Babylonians carried away cultic items from the Jerusalem temple and placed them in the temple of Marduk (II Chr. 36:7, Ezra 5:14; cf. I Sam 5:1-2). In the worldview of the ancient Fertile Crescent, the defeat of a nation necessarily implied the defeat of the nation's patron god (cf. Exod. 12:12, II Kgs. 18:30-35). It would not have required a great leap for Judean thinkers in Babylon to see the application of the resurrection rites of Marduk to their own god.

It appears that the Judean scribes of the exile did indeed borrow this idea. They chose Noah (^(lú)HUN.GA₂ = *Dumuzi*) as their version of Ziusura-Atraḥāsis-Utnapištim with a precise purpose in mind. He built a boat called "*Tabû*" (TAB.U), representing the 12 tribes of Israel. The boat was 300 cubits in length. This number was conceptualized as "60 x 5" (GEŠ₂.IA₂).⁵⁷ The number 60 can be written with the logogram "KU", signifying "to bear, procreate, produce" (Sum. ugu₄).^{3,12} The same sign signifies "destiny" (NAM₂).^{3,12} Thus, the product of "Yah" (IA₂) and "destiny" (NAM₂) gives us the ship's length (5 x 60 = 300). Length is associated in both Hebrew (ךר—'rk) and Akkadian (*arāku*) with the benediction of "long life". Since the Ark (*Tabû*) is "Zl", the length formula invokes a destiny of long life (Akk. *napištu arāku*), including divinely-aided procreation. Dumuzi was the god who ensured fertility and renewal. It was the change of fate the Judeans sought in the liver of the *barû* ram.

By the Late Babylonian period, the constellation ^(lú)HUN.GA₂ (Gr. *Aries*) was commonly called "LU" (Lafitte, 2009).⁵⁸ In Sumerian, "lu" refers to a "ram" or "sheep", but also designates "man, men, people".³ As a verb, it means "to make numerous, abundant, to multiply".³ Hence, "LU" has both individual and collective connotations. It connects Noah to the Ark (*Tabû* > Zl = *Life*) via the cuneiform symbolism of the Hebraic protagonist.

The Old Babylonian sign "LU" (𒌒) is "LAGAB x BAR"—literally a box enclosing the symbol signifying "foreign" and "to open, to uncover, expose, to see, to remove, to release" (in Sumerian).^{3,12,59} "Bar" also means "liver".¹⁴ In the narrative context of the Deluge, the logogram evokes the opening of the Ark/Ram by ^dUtu (and the *barû* priest), who must

⁵⁷ Labat (1948) lists "GEŠIA" (5 x 60 =) 300 (p. 247). Given that Sum. "geš₂" = 60 and "ia₂" = 5 (ePSD), it should be written "GEŠ₂.IA₂". In the Genesis context, it works as a pun: "geš₂.IA₂"—"Tree of Éa" or "Tool of Éa".

⁵⁸ Lafitte (2009) traces the evolution of the constellation name "MUL LU₂.HUN.GA₂" as a function of the telescoping of logograms over time: just as "𒌒BAR₂" (*Nisānu*) became "𒌒BAR", the short form "LU₂" transitioned to "LU" (p. 102).

⁵⁹ The symbol "BAR" (𒌒) is difficult to distinguish from "MAŠ" (𒌒) in cuneiform tablets from the Kassite period onward (Clay, 1909). The sign embodies the root concept of Akkadian magic, "*mašmašūtu*" (MAŠ.MAŠ). Given the implicit duality of the pair (MAŠ signifies *twin*), "MAŠ.MAŠ" may be "MAŠ.BAR"—the "uncovering" and "removal" of evil (or vice-versa in magical assaults).

determine the fate of the supplicant. The Neo-Babylonian sign “LU” (𒌦) also represents “DIB” and “AD₃”.¹² The first evokes “wrath” (of deities), “to hold, seize, bind, tie up, take away” and “to traverse, cross, wander” in Sumerian.^{3,7,14} The second originated as “LU X BAD”—signifying “corpse” and “to open, let out, release”.^{3,14,12} By making Dumuzi the man/ram/people (LU) of the Ark, the Judean scribes invoked the cosmic power of the god who rises from the dead on behalf of the nation—adapting the role of Marduk on the first day of the Akītu Festival in the month of Nisānu (Sum. *nisan*, signifying *First Fruits*).

The Judean scribes underscore this symbolism by specifying that the flood concluded on the 1st day of the first month (*Nisan*). It contrasts with the beginning of the flood in the previous year during the “second month” (Gen. 7:11), which is Akkadian “Ayyāru” (*a-a-ru*)—a wordplay signifying “to send waters” in Sumerian.^{2,3} The semantic field includes “yarūru”—a musical shout of either lamentation or joy.^{2,7,60} In personal names, “a-ar” means “praise” (Sum. *ar₂*), connecting once again to “יהודה”—“Yehudah” (cf. Scheil, 1900, p. 28: *A-ar Ili*). The month was also called “Yeru”.² It therefore appears that the Judean scribes chose the month as a cryptic reference to the destruction of Judah and Jerusalem.

This conclusion is supported by the scribal placement of the flood in the 600th year of Noah's life (Gen. 7:6).⁶¹ Cuneiform numbers can be either spelled syllabically or represented by logograms. These numerals can also form numerically-based words (de Ridder, 2021). The cuneiform number 600 (*AŠ₄.ME*) invokes the symbol of the sun god and divine judge, Šamaš (*AŠ.ME* = Akk. *šamšatu*).^{3,7} This meaning weighs on one side of the scales. It counterbalances the evil symbols of the moon god on the other side.

Hebrew “שש” (*šeš*—six) is a homophone of “ŠEŠ” (*URU₃*)—the sign of Sîn (and the city of Ur). Sumerian “six” (*aš₃*) is a homophone of “curse” (*aš₂*).³ The Akkadian word “hundred” (*me'atu*, *mātu*) can also mean “native land” (*mātu*) and “to die” (*mātu*). The phrase “שש מאות שנה” (*šeš me'ot šanah*—six hundred year) reconstructs as Akkadian “*MU šediš me'atu*”. “Šediš” (Akk. *six*) can be written “ŠE₃ + DIŠ” (𒌦). These two signs combine to form Neo-Babylonian version of the sign “LU” (𒌦)—the “ram/people”. The number names the year (*MU*) of the death of the nation, setting up the reversal of fate in the grand finale of the Hebraic account—via the *barû* ram.⁶²

⁶⁰ The form “*ayyarūrūtu*” can be read as a “*lamentation to* ^(d)*Utu*”.

⁶¹ Note that “six-hundred” in Genesis pays homage to Atra-ḫāsis: Sum. “*ge-eš-tu*” (600) ~ “*geštug*”, “*giš-túg*” ~ Akk. “*ḫasīsu*” (SL, CAD). Akk. “*atru*” (*DIRI = SI.A*) means “reed raft” and “to inundate with water” (i.e. to flood).

⁶² Sum. “*mu*” also means “line on a tablet”, “oath” and “to name, speak” and “son, written name, good name, repute, fame” (SL). It plays upon Akk. “*mû*”—signifying “water” and “cosmic order, cultic rules” (CDA).

The Ark was opened in the 601st year of Noah's life (Gen. 8:13).⁴⁹ The addition of “one” (Akk. *ištēnu*) to “six hundred” contains the substitution “*tēnû*”. The root word “*enû*” signifies to “reassign” an omen and to “alter” a judgment.⁷ The subject of this transformation is literally “*IŠ*”, which is Akkadian “herdsman” or shepherd (*kizû*).² The sign “*IŠ*” is also “*KUKKUDA*” (*kúkku-da: bound in darkness*).^{3,12} In Hebrew, “*IŠ*” (יֵשׁ) is equivalent to “*LU*”, symbolizing the man and the *barû* ram. It is a 7-way wordplay anchored in the Old Babylonian sign “*LU*” (𒌦) containing “*BAR*”—meaning “*liver*” and “*to set free captives*” (Akk. *uššuru*).^{7,12}

These elements suggest that the Hebraic Ark tablet was composed in Babylonia for use in *barû* rituals performed in the Judean exile community. It further suggests recitation during the spring Akītu festival in Judean towns such as Al Yahūdu.^{50,63} The story (like the Exodus) culminates in the month of Nisan, making it appropriate for this season. After the return of the exiles, these works became the Judean national epic—read aloud during the reconceptualized “*Passover*”.⁶⁴ However, the post-exilic commemorative holiday obscured the original purpose and de-linked the underlying themes of the Arks of Moses and Noah.

The Judean adaptation of this ancient Mesopotamian myth invoked the nation's escape from servitude under ^d30 (Sin) and ^d50 (Marduk)—the two “ruling” gods of Babylon in the mid-6th century BC. The cryptic language and symbolism of the Judean scribes circumvented the Prime Directive of their era, making the authors and their nation the allies of the wise and crafty Éa in his ancient battle against of the forces of destruction.

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⁶³ For Al Yahūdu, see Pearce and Wunsch (2014).

⁶⁴ For the new “אֲנֹכְחִי” (*Psh'*), see Crowley (1923, introduction; cf. Ezra 6:19-22).

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